

Master Thesis

The Impact of Policies for Surface Water Protection During Wet Weather

Prototype of an Agent-Based Model to Assess
Non-Technical Challenges to Monitoring CSOs

Samuel Derwort

(October 2020 – April 2021)

Remark:

This is not the original master thesis and was adapted after completion to ensure anonymity (11.05.2021).

Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich

Eigenständigkeitserklärung

Die unterzeichnete Eigenständigkeitserklärung ist Bestandteil jeder während des Studiums verfassten Semester-, Bachelor- und Master-Arbeit oder anderen Abschlussarbeit (auch der jeweils elektronischen Version).

Die Dozentinnen und Dozenten können auch für andere bei ihnen verfasste schriftliche Arbeiten eine Eigenständigkeitserklärung verlangen.

Ich bestätige, die vorliegende Arbeit selbständig und in eigenen Worten verfasst zu haben. Davon ausgenommen sind sprachliche und inhaltliche Korrekturvorschläge durch die Betreuer und Betreuerinnen der Arbeit.

Titel der Arbeit (in Druckschrift):

The Impact of Policies for Surface Water Protection During Wet Weather
Prototype of an Agent-Based Model to Assess Non-Technical Challenges to Monitoring CSOs

Verfasst von (in Druckschrift):

Bei Gruppenarbeiten sind die Namen aller Verfasserinnen und Verfasser erforderlich.

Name(n):

Derwort

Vorname(n):

Samuel

Ich bestätige mit meiner Unterschrift:

- Ich habe keine im Merkblatt „Zitier-Knigge“ beschriebene Form des Plagiats begangen.
- Ich habe alle Methoden, Daten und Arbeitsabläufe wahrheitsgetreu dokumentiert.
- Ich habe keine Daten manipuliert.
- Ich habe alle Personen erwähnt, welche die Arbeit wesentlich unterstützt haben.

Ich nehme zur Kenntnis, dass die Arbeit mit elektronischen Hilfsmitteln auf Plagiate überprüft werden kann.

Ort, Datum

Zürich, 22.06.2020

Unterschrift(en)

S. Derwort

Bei Gruppenarbeiten sind die Namen aller Verfasserinnen und Verfasser erforderlich. Durch die Unterschriften bürgen sie gemeinsam für den gesamten Inhalt dieser schriftlichen Arbeit.

Abstract

During wet weather, combined sewer overflow (CSO) tanks discharge wastewater into the environment to reduce the load on the wastewater treatment plant. In Switzerland, it is currently unknown how much exactly these discharges contribute to the pollution of receiving waters. This gap of knowledge could be overcome through the installation of cost-effective sensor technology in the CSO tanks and the regular evaluation of the monitoring data. The majority of Swiss wastewater associations do not evaluate the monitoring data more than once a year or aggregate it to a lower temporal resolution, which diminishes the data's potential performance-based compliance assessment and better planning of future infrastructure. This lack of evidence stands in stark contrast to the high requirements towards data management and large financial investments in wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). As practical technological solutions for sensor and data transfer technologies exist, as well as role-model utilities, which use the data effectively, the deficits are most probably political and organizational.

However, it is unclear which policies can be recommended to overcome these obstacles. With a focus on the behavior and interactions of stakeholders of Swiss urban drainage management, this master thesis aims at evaluating policies to improve sensor adoption in CSO tanks. A prototype of an agent-based model (ABM) is developed based on theoretical concepts from psychology and social simulation, as well as context knowledge, e.g. for the choice of the stakeholders. To assess the potential for an empirically grounded ABM, data sets of different categories are combined and integrated into the prototype. During the process of data collection, a novel data set from Chestonag was obtained. To include urban drainage management practice, a quality check is performed via a rule-book-like list of assumptions and interviews with domain experts from cantonal authorities. For demonstration purposes, three different scenarios are developed evaluating the impact of the following policies: i) the planning instrument GEP ('Generelle Entwässerungsplanung'), ii) a regulation requiring the installation of sensors in CSO tanks, and iii) better monitoring technology. These are supplemented by four numerical experiments to assess the behavior and uncertainties of the model. In addition, a sensitivity analysis is performed using a simple screening method.

Results from the scenarios for policy evaluation suggest that policy ii) is most effective. The model predicts that most agents adopt sensors shortly after the start of the simulation period in 2017, with a decreasing adoption rate after several years. However, as the ABM is a prototype, absolute results are not reliable, and also relative results have to be carefully examined. Interestingly, the sensitivity analysis reveals that the initial parameters of the agents have a high impact on the model output. The limited availability of empirical data, e.g. historical data of sensor adoption, to initialize the agent parameters leads to great uncertainties. Therefore, model parameters were adjusted ad hoc and an empirical validation is not possible. However, experts at least partly agreed to the assumptions that were taken regarding Swiss urban drainage management.

In conclusion, an ABM developed for the analysis of policies cannot be expected to have predictive power, unless suitable data sets are available, which is a common challenge to ABMs. In fact, particular data sets simply might not be obtainable, such as historical data of sensor adoption. Nevertheless, the approach of ABM can be useful for system understanding. Taking a multidisciplinary approach of ABM has contributed a new understanding of the deficits regarding sensor adoption and opened up new paths for research. Further work should concentrate on data collection, the refinement of the agent behavior model using the Theory of Planned Behavior and the opinion dynamics model using survey data that is currently collected in the scope of the POLAAR project.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Prof. Dr. Max Maurer for giving me the opportunity to write my Master's thesis at Eawag and his valuable feedback. My special thanks go to Liliane Manny and Dr. Jörg Rieckermann. I was lucky to write my thesis under their passionate supervision, receiving twice the usual amount of support. They were always there to answer my questions and broadened my horizon with their ideas and inputs. Not only did they give me a lot of their time to introduce me into the world of urban drainage, but also to motivate me and showing me new paths to follow.

I would also like to thank Dr. Juan Pablo Carbajal, whose advice was not only useful for developing the model, but who also took his time to share his knowledge of programming with me. Furthermore, I would like to thank Dr. Manuel Fischer and Kukka IImanen for their feedback and advice during the intermediate presentations. Reto Battaglia and Hans Balmer contributed to this Master thesis by taking their time to fill out my questionnaire and freely providing their expertise and materials, for which I am very grateful. Furthermore, I would like to thank Chestonag Automation AG for providing a data set about CSO tanks.

Finally, I would like to thank my family and my girlfriend for always supporting me, my grandma for hosting me on the countryside, and my father for lending me another laptop to run simulations.

Contents

Abstract	iii
Symbols	xv
1 Introduction	1
2 Materials and Methods	3
2.1 Agent-Based Modeling	3
2.2 Organization of Swiss Urban Drainage Management	4
2.3 Agent-Based Model for Sensor Adoption	5
2.3.1 Simplification of the Stakeholders	6
2.3.2 Behavior Model	7
2.3.3 Opinion Dynamics	8
2.3.4 Model Input	9
2.3.5 Agent Parameters from Prior Knowledge	11
2.3.6 The Stakeholders' Social Network	13
2.4 Plausibility	15
2.5 Scenarios	15
2.5.1 Baseline Scenario	16
2.5.2 The Impact of Selected Policies on Sensor Adoption	16
2.6 Analysis of the Prototype	17
2.6.1 Numerical Experiments	17
2.6.2 Sensitivity Analysis	17
2.6.3 Implementation	18
3 Results	19
3.1 Scenarios	19
3.1.1 Baseline Scenario	19
3.1.2 Scenarios for Policy Evaluation	20
3.2 Analysis of the Prototype	21
3.2.1 Numerical Experiments	21
3.2.2 Sensitivity Analysis	21
4 Discussion	25
4.1 Scenarios	25
4.1.1 Baseline Scenario and Parameter Adjustment	25
4.1.2 Scenarios for Policy Evaluation	25
4.2 Analysis of the Prototype	26
4.2.1 Numerical Experiments	26
4.2.2 Sensitivity Analysis	27
4.3 Plausibility	27
4.3.1 Theory of Planned Behavior	27
4.3.2 Expert Discussion	27
4.3.3 Validation	28
4.3.4 Empirical Data	28
4.4 Are ABMs useful?	29
4.5 Software implementation	29
5 Conclusion	30
A Implementation in Python	36

B	Organization of Urban Drainage	37
B.1	Evaluation of Data Sets concerning CSO Tanks	40
B.2	Policies	42
C	Data	43
C.1	Overview	43
C.1.1	Survey wastewater associations	43
C.1.2	Interviews & survey cantonal authorities	43
C.1.3	Chestonag Aussenbauwerke	44
C.1.4	WWTPs and catchment areas geodata	44
C.1.5	Municipality survey	44
C.1.6	Geodata Switzerland	44
C.1.7	CSO tank survey canton Bern	45
D	Agent Parameters from Survey Data	46
E	Relative Agreement Algorithm	51
F	Scenarios and Numerical Experiments	52
F.1	Scenario 1 - Baseline Scenario (GEP)	52
F.2	Scenario 1 - Without GEP	57
F.3	Scenario 2 - Regulation	57
F.4	Scenario 3 - Better Technology	58
F.5	Numerical experiment 1 - Shifted communication schedule	58
F.6	Numerical experiment 2 - Different communication schedule	59
F.7	Numerical experiment 3 - Cantonal authorities' network	60
F.8	Numerical experiment 4 - Random opinion uncertainty	60
G	Sensitivity Analysis	61
G.1	Parameter range	61
G.2	Sampling Agent Parameters	61
G.3	Additional Results	63
G.3.1	Full scatter plot by parameters	63
G.3.2	Other performance metrics	63
H	Development History	69
H.1	Starting point	69
H.2	Model 1	69
H.3	Model 2	73
I	Expert Questionnaires	78

List of Figures

2.1	Illustration of different operation and ownership situations.	5
2.2	An overview of the model with annotated section numbers.	6
2.3	Simplified stakeholders of CSOs in Switzerland.	6
2.4	Original and simplified schema for TPB. The schema on the left was adapted from [Ajzen, 2013]. The simplification of TPB for the prototype consists in combining the factors 'attitude' and 'subjective norm' to a single variable <i>sia</i> and removing the influence of the perceived behavioral control <i>pbc</i> on the intention. The behavior is performed if $sia > sia_threshold$ and $pbc > pbc_threshold$	8
2.5	Flowchart of the model describing the behavior of each agent. After the agents are initialized with the variables <i>sia</i> , <i>pbc</i> , and <i>u</i> , the RA Algorithm proceeds each time step and the agents modify each others values for <i>sia</i> and <i>u</i> , as it is illustrated in Figure 2.5. The chosen time step is one month. If an agent's <i>sia</i> crosses the attitude threshold <i>sia_threshold</i> while the agent's <i>pbc</i> is above the <i>pbc_threshold</i> , the agent adopts a sensor. Only municipalities and WWTP operators are considered to adopt sensors. The other agent types only participate in the exchange of <i>sia</i> . The communication between agent types is determined through the communication schedule.	10
2.6	The parameters <i>sia</i> and <i>pbc</i> of the evaluated survey respondents (wastewater associations)	13
2.7	The parameters <i>sia</i> , <i>pbc</i> , and <i>u</i> for WWTP operators and cantonal authorities. . .	14
3.1	Overview of all scenarios and numerical experiments. The share of municipalities after a 10 years simulation period, 100 iterations each scenario / numerical experiment. Notable is Exp. 4, where the results show a wider variation due to the random assignment of the uncertainty <i>u</i> . Sc. 2 shows the highest share of agents with sensors. Figure F.1 in the appendix is the corresponding plot for the WWTP operators.	19
3.2	The share of WWTP operators with sensors over the simulation period of 10 years in the baseline scenario, while the parameter μ is varied. (Average of 20 runs for each value). It can be seen that with a higher value of μ , the sensor adoption rate is higher at the beginning of the simulation period.	20
3.3	Results of the scenarios for policy evaluation described in Table 2.4. The scenario 'regulation' shows the largest increase concerning the shares of agents with sensors. (Average of 100 runs for each scenario)	21
3.4	Results of the numerical experiments described in Table 2.4. Compared to the other numerical experiments, a notable increase in Exp. 4 'opinion dynamics' can be seen. (Average of 100 runs for each numerical experiment)	22
3.5	Opinion dynamics including 482 agents (eastern Switzerland) - uncertainty <i>u</i> was assigned inverse proportionally to the extremity of the opinion ($u = 0.51 - sia - 0.5 $). A polarization is observed.	23
3.6	Opinion dynamics including 482 agents (eastern Switzerland) - uncertainty <i>u</i> was assigned randomly (0.01-1). The agents' attitudes converge at intermediate values.	23
3.7	Morris screening co-variance plot for the total of Municipalities with sensors in 2027 (after 120 timesteps of 1 month), 600 iterations total for the whole of Switzerland. In the plot on the left, the values for the absolute value of the mean μ^* and standard deviation σ are shown. In the scatter plot on the right, the relation between μ^* and σ is illustrated. The farther from the origin a point is, the higher the influence of the parameter.	24

3.8	Morris screening co-variance plot for the increase of WWTP operators with sensors from 2017 to 2027, 600 iterations total for the whole of Switzerland. In the plot on the left, the values for the absolute value of the mean μ^* and standard deviation σ are shown. In the scatter plot on the right, the relation between μ^* and σ is illustrated. The farther from the origin a point is, the higher the influence of the parameter.	24
B.1	Illustration of the Motivation for this Master Thesis. On the top left, an average CSO operator without sensor is shown. on the top right, an exemplary CSO operator is shown. The two figures on the bottom represent the current (left) and ideal (right) situation in Switzerland. The goal of this master thesis is to analyze policies that increase sensor adoption.	37
B.2	Results concerning wastewater/urban drainage of the survey 'Nationale Gemeinde-schreiberbefragung 2017' [Ladner, 2017]. 903 of the municipality officials claimed that the municipality organizes wastewater/urban drainage on its own, while 823 of them are organized in some form of collaboration with other municipalities or private providers.	38
B.3	The stakeholders of wastewater treatment and urban drainage management of a WWTP catchment area including the relations between the different stakeholders. The real stakeholders are assigned the agent categories used in this Master's thesis by color. Original graph by Kukka Ilmanen â Präsentation Sozio-Technische Netzwerke Umfrage 22.09.2020, Eawag	39
B.4	The amount of WWTP operators that operate a certain number of CSO tanks. The Data Sets C.1.7, C.1.1, and C.1.3 were combined. The latter data set also includes other special constructions ('Aussenwerke').	41
B.5	The amount of CSO tanks by different WWTPs vs the size of the WWTPs. The Data Sets C.1.7, C.1.1, and C.1.3 were combined. The latter data set also includes other special constructions ('Aussenwerke').	41
B.6	Table containing the ranking of policies resulting from the survey conducted among wastewater associations and cantonal authorities [Manny, 2017].	42
D.1	The unnormalized results from the calculation according to Table 2.1 and 2.2. . . .	47
D.2	The parameters <i>sia</i> and <i>pbc</i> of the survey respondents by WWTP size.	48
F.1	Overview of all scenarios and numerical experiments. The share of WWTP operators after a 10 years simulation period, 100 iterations each scenario / numerical experiment. Sc. 2 and 3 show the highest share of agents with sensors. Compared to Figure 3.1, a smaller variation of the results is observed for the WWTP operators. The reason for this is the initialization of the agents' <i>sia</i> , <i>pbc</i> , and <i>u</i> , that are sampled randomly each iteration for the municipalities, but not for the WWTP operators.	52
F.2	The share of WWTP operators with sensors over the simulation period of 10 years in the baseline scenario, while the parameter <i>sia.threshold</i> is varied. (20 runs for each value). It can be seen that with a lower value of <i>sia.threshold</i> , the share of WWTP operators with sensors is higher. For a value of <i>sia.threshold</i> , a jump is observed in the first time step, when the agents with <i>sia</i> higher than the threshold adopt sensors.	54
F.3	The share of municipalities with sensors over the simulation period of 10 years in the baseline scenario, while the parameter <i>sia.threshold</i> is varied. (20 runs for each value). It can be seen that with a lower value of <i>sia.threshold</i> , the share of municipalities with sensors is higher.	55
F.4	The share of WWTP operators with sensors over the simulation period of 10 years in the baseline scenario, while the parameter <i>pbc.threshold</i> is varied. (20 runs for each value). It can be seen that with a lower value of <i>sia.threshold</i> , the share of WWTP operators with sensors is higher.	56

F.5	Opinion dynamics including 2966 agents for Scenario 2 'regulation'. The increase of <i>sia</i> through the regulation affects all agents that have not adopted sensors (yet). The municipalities are most affected by the regulation that increases their <i>sia</i> over the <i>sia_threshold</i> , while the increase of <i>sia</i> is not strong enough for a large part of the WWTP operators to adopt sensors.	58
G.1	The distributions from which the agent parameters are sampled.	62
G.2	Total share of municipalities with sensors after 120 time steps by entry parameter.	64
G.3	Increase of share of WWTP operators (from t0 to t120) with sensors after 120 time steps by entry parameter.	65
G.4	Morris co-variance plot: increase of share of WWTP operators (from t0 to t120) with sensors.	66
G.5	Morris co-variance plot: total share of Municipalities with sensors after 120 time steps.	66
G.6	Morris co-variance plot: The analyzed metric is the increase ('jump') of WWTP operators (above) and municipalities (below) with sensors after the first time step (from t0 to t1) which occurs due to all agents that are initialized with <i>sia</i> above the threshold adopting sensors.	67
G.7	Morris co-variance plot: The analyzed metric is the increase of WWTP operators (above) and municipalities (below) with sensors between the first time step and the last one (from t0 to t120)	68
H.1	The first model draft including one catchment area. In the boxes of the agents, the agent behavior is described in a pseudo-algorithm.	69
H.2	The hierarchy of subsystems regarding the first model draft.	70
H.3	Schema of the first implemented model. The pseudo-algorithm of agent-behavior is included in the descriptive boxes of each agent type.	71
H.4	Test network for the first implemented model.	72
H.5	Results of the 'awareness'-model running on the test network. The different colors illustrate the share of aware agents for different awareness thresholds.	72
H.6	The 'awareness' model flowchart, including factor P.	74
H.7	Varying P for all agents in the 'awareness' model simultaneously for the whole of Switzerland.	75
H.8	Varying P for the WWTP operator agents while the other agents' P is kept at 0.2. Eastern Switzerland included.	75
H.9	Varying P for the municipality agents while the other agents' P is kept at 0.2. Eastern Switzerland included.	76
H.10	Varying P for the cantonal authority agents while the other agents' P is kept at 0.2. Eastern Switzerland included.	76
H.11	The extended 'awareness' model flowchart, including financial, know-how, and decision power layer.	77

List of Tables

2.1	Calculation of <i>sia</i> from wastewater association survey. In the column 'weighting' the cursive words designate the quantity given in the 'quantity' column. For further information, see Appendix D.	12
2.2	Calculation of <i>pbc</i> from wastewater association survey	12
2.3	The number of agents and links between them in the generated network of Switzerland	15
2.4	Overview of scenarios and numerical experiments	16
F.1	Communication schedule baseline scenario - frequency table (meeting every X months)	53
F.2	Communication schedule baseline scenario - start table (first meeting after X months)	53
F.3	Communication schedule model configuration 6 - frequency table (meeting every X months)	57
F.4	Communication schedule model configuration 2 - start table (first meeting after X months)	59
F.5	Communication schedule model configuration 3 - frequency table (meeting every X months)	60
G.1	Parameter bounds for the sensitivity analysis	63

Symbols

Acronyms and Abbreviations

ETH	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule
Eawag	Eidgenössische Anstalt für Wasserversorgung, Abwasserreinigung und Gewässerschutz
SWW	Siedlungswasserwirtschaft
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
CSO	Combined Sewer Overflow
ABM	Agent-Based Model
TPB	Theory of Planned Behavior
<i>sia</i>	Sensor Installation Attitude
<i>pb</i>	Perceived Behavioral Control
<i>u</i>	Uncertainty (of Opinion)
RA	Relative Agreement (Algorithm)

1 Introduction

During wet weather, the amount of water in a combined urban drainage system can exceed the inlet capacity of a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). To relieve the WWTP and ensure its undisturbed operation, the waste- and rainwater mixture is retained in the urban drainage system and afterwards slowly passed on to the WWTP. One type of infrastructure to achieve this are **combined sewer overflow (CSO)** tanks¹, containing a limited storage volume for waste- and rainwater. If the water level in the CSO tank rises above a certain threshold during a wet weather event, the excess water overflows untreated into the receiving water body.

Not enough dynamic monitoring data is available. How much these CSO events contribute to the pollution of water bodies has not exactly been quantified yet. Not enough dynamic monitoring data about discharge frequency, duration and volume is available, such that these quantities have to be estimated for the European Union [Pistocchi and Dorati, 2018] and Switzerland [Mutzner et al., 2016]. Even though CSOs may be a source of pollution as significant as WWTPs for some substances [Dittmer, 2015], the quality, reliability, comparability, and evaluation of monitoring data is still insufficient in the german-speaking region (D-A-CH) [Hoppe et al., 2019].

Utilities collect monitoring data, but usually do not exploit its full potential. In a survey among wastewater associations² [Manny, 2017], 94% of the Swiss associations were found to have at least one sensor installed in a CSO tank, most of which transfer the data to a process control system³. However, only 19% claimed to evaluate the measured time series from sensors in CSO tanks more than once a year and one third of the associations would aggregate the data to hourly resolution [Manny et al., 2019]. The infrequent evaluation does not exploit the actual potential of the data. Due the aggregation, the information about CSO duration or volume is lost, as well as the monitoring data's potential to validate hydrodynamic models. Only few of the associations transfer the data to engineers or authorities for planning of future infrastructure and compliance assessment, respectively. Furthermore, it is assumed that some associations unfamiliar with sensor technology in CSOs have not responded to the survey. The municipalities that operate their own WWTP were not targeted in the scope of the survey. In general, it is assumed that the municipalities have less professional and economic resources than wastewater associations.

Monitoring data is useful. The two reasons for monitoring technology in CSO tanks most frequently mentioned by wastewater associations in the survey were the continuous supervision of CSO tanks, followed by the understanding of the urban drainage system's behavior. The measured duration of CSO events could be used for the calibration and validation of sewer hydrodynamic models [Montserrat et al., 2016] or for performance-based compliance assessment. Potential lies also in the use of sensor data as basis for planning infrastructure and ensuring the efficient use of infrastructure.

Sensors for CSO monitoring are cost-effective. In the future, more heavy rainfalls due to climate change will pose challenges to the sewage infrastructure [Hoffmann, 2014]. As increasing the capacity of sewage infrastructure is costly and comes along with a low efficiency in utilization, dynamic solutions such as smart stormwater systems [Kerkez et al., 2016] provide an opportunity. In order for smart stormwater system to function, monitoring data, transmitted to the SCADA system in real-time, is crucial.

It could be done with relatively few investments. In Comparison to monitoring data from CSOs, a lot of data is available for WWTPs in Switzerland, with automatized evaluation at the

¹In general, 'CSO' (Combined sewer overflow) refers to the event of discharging mixed wastewater and 'CSO tank' to the infrastructure element. However, a 'CSO tank' might sometimes be referred to as 'CSO' for reasons of brevity.

²In Switzerland, the operation of CSO tanks traditionally falls into the responsibility of municipalities. Many of them collaborate with neighboring municipalities and are organized into wastewater associations for the operation of a WWTP and potentially the urban drainage infrastructure including CSO tanks.

³e.g. SCADA system (Supervisory control and data acquisition system)

end of the year. Furthermore, some progressive wastewater associations have already implemented sensor technology in their CSO tanks and regularly evaluate the discharged volume during CSO events [AVA, 2020]. The supervision of CSO tanks can be achieved with a rather simple water level meter, mostly using sonar or pressure sensors [Baumann, 2017]. While the introduction of a fourth purification stage in WWTPs requires 1.2 billion CHF of initial investments [Eawag, 2015], sensor installation in CSO tanks and data management seem like relatively cheap measures to improve surface water protection [Manny et al., 2019]. The cost of a sensor is negligible opposed to investments in building CSO tanks, but even the continuous investments for data evaluation only amount to a few per mille of the investment costs [Hoppe et al., 2016].

The barriers are of political / organizational nature. The barriers to a evidence-based management of CSO infrastructure need political and organizational improvements [Rieckermann et al., 2017]. As the technological means are available, good practices for data management need to be established. Some states in Germany are ahead of Switzerland and Austria concerning regulation. In the UK, surface water protection could be substantially improved by changing organizational structures [Clifforde et al., 2006]. Furthermore, a lot of potential for collaboration concerning data management between WWTPs and urban drainage lies fallow, e.g. every WWTP has a process control system where CSO sensors could be integrated.

Agent-Based Models (ABM) are used in different but similar domains. In order to better understand political and organizational barriers and to test possible policies that enhance sensor adoption, the method of agent-based modeling (ABM) is chosen. ABMs constitute a quantitative method making it possible to model the interactions of individuals or other entities ('agents') in a bottom-up manner. When a system features interacting, heterogeneous agents and social complexity, ABMs often remain the only suitable approach to model or reproduce it [Conte and Paolucci, 2014]. While it might in some cases not be possible to formulate a model of the entire system, the individual parts of the system can be modeled. The dynamic nature of ABMs allow to model the impact of policies, which cannot be achieved with e.g. a simple regression. With increasing computational power and available data, they have become more popular over the recent years. Application domains include energy systems [Singh, 2016], traffic modeling [Saprykin et al., 2019] or the spread of epidemics [Marini et al., 2020] to support decision and policy-makers. ABMs are also used in computational social sciences [Helbing, 2012]. ABMs have been used in the water sector [Tillman, 2001] for modeling the building of capacity in water pipes or for the adaptation of renewable energy technologies [Rai and Robinson, 2015]. The latter provides a methodological guideline for this Master's thesis.

In this Master's thesis, a prototype of an ABM is developed and implemented. The model simulates the behavior and interactions of stakeholders in Swiss urban drainage management and aims at evaluating different policies enhancing sensor adoption in CSO tanks. The development of an ABM prototype extends over several domains. The context of the model is analyzed through the collection and analysis of data as well as expert consultations. Subsequently, the prototype is developed and implemented in Python and different scenarios are run. This master thesis seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How can stakeholder behavior and interactions be modeled?
2. How can available prior knowledge and data be integrated into an ABM prototype for CSO sensor adoption in Switzerland?
3. What are effective policies that increase sensor adoption?
4. What are the largest uncertainties inherent in the ABM prototype?
5. What is necessary for the development of a plausible ABM in the context of sensor adoption in CSO tanks?
6. Is the approach of ABM useful in the context of sensor adoption in CSO tanks?

2 Materials and Methods

At the beginning of this chapter, an overview about the approach of ABM is given. This is followed by a description of the context the model is situated in, introducing the stakeholders involved in Swiss urban drainage management. Afterwards, the developed ABM prototype is described, how the real-world stakeholders are simplified such that their behavior and interactions can be implemented on a computer. The theoretical models to describe the agents' behavior and the opinion exchange algorithm governing the interactions are presented, followed by an overview of the model structure and input. Then, it is explained how the model input is generated from prior knowledge and empirical data. Before scenarios for policy evaluation and numerical experiments for uncertainty analysis are described, the methods for rooting the model in urban drainage management practice are presented. Finally, a sensitivity analysis is performed through a simple screening method.

2.1 Agent-Based Modeling

The notion of an 'agent' in the context of ABM usually describes an autonomous entity that can change its (computational) states and interacts with other agents in a common environment. However, this general concept is applied to agents of various levels of complexity and properties, from acting according to simple decision rules to learning or the adaptation to other agents or the environment.

Short History of ABM

ABMs need large computational resources and thus have not become widely popular before the 1990s. A famous early example of an agent-based simulation was Conway's Game of Life [Gardner, 1970], a so-called cellular automaton. In Conway's Game of Life, self-replicating patterns emerge from very simple rules for grid cells that are either alive or dead, depending on the number of alive neighbors. Meanwhile, these simple rules have advanced to neural network models, capable of producing self-regenerating images and patterns that originate from a single grid cell [Mordvintsev et al., 2020]. One of the first agent-based model concepts used in a social context was the Schelling segregation model [Schelling, 1971], showing the emergence of segregation among agents of different types with a small preference for agents similar to themselves.

ABMs are used in various domains. The ABM approach has been adopted by various domains due to its versatility. For example, it can be applied in large scale traffic simulations [Saprykin et al., 2019], modeling electricity transmission [Singh, 2016], or the spread of epidemics [Marini et al., 2020]. Also in the domain of urban water management, ABMs have been developed. They can be used to gain insight about complex systems involving various stakeholders interacting with each other and sharing a common environment [Tillman, 2001, Berglund, 2015], which is useful for evaluating policies and providing support to decision-makers. There exist also technical applications using an agent-based approach, such as agent-based control schemes for water systems [Kerkez et al., 2016]. In social sciences, ABMs are used to investigate tipping points at which the system will change its regime. For example, under which circumstances cooperation between agents can emerge [Helbing, 2012, p. 131-138]. The study of social tipping dynamics is of interest regarding the challenges facing humanity such as climate change which require large-scale adjustments of society [Otto et al., 2020]. However, the modeling of socio-economic systems faces challenges that are absent in e.g. engineering sciences [Helbing, 2012, p. 1-22]. Often, ABMs constitute an act of balance between the complexity of the real world and the pressure for minimal 'publishable' models that can be implemented [Conte and Paolucci, 2014]. For social sciences, this minimalist approach is sometimes unfavorable [Helbing, 2012, p. 1-22].

The validation of ABMs is a challenge. ABMs are used to model a large variety of systems, which comes along with a multitude of different solutions for different problems. ABM is still an emerging research area and efforts are undertaken to formalize ABMs and make them comparable

through a standardized approach, e.g. the ODD+ protocol [Grimm et al., 2010], to develop a 'toolbox' that will facilitate the development of ABMs in the future. Due to the currently still limited formalism of ABMs, the reliability of ABMs for prediction rather than exploration is disputed [Manzo, 2014]. The versatility of the concept of ABMs leads to modeling methods that differ from case to case, which poses a new challenge for every model. For example, in some cases the validation of an ABM is done through experts and comparison to real world data [Tillman, 2001], while the model is not calibrated. In more recent ABMs, the models are based on theoretical concepts and then calibrated and validated using empirical (historical) data [Rai and Robinson, 2015, Caprioli et al., 2020] and sensitivity analysis. In these cases, not the states of individual agents are validated through the empirical data, but the aggregated model output. However, a compromise has to be found on a case-to-case basis depending on the available data [Manzo, 2014] and a model can only be validated if enough empirical data is available. Which empirical data would be needed for validation in the case of ABM for sensor adoption is investigated in this master thesis.

Despite of limitations and challenges, ABM constitutes an interesting approach for modeling the adoption of sensors in CSO tanks due to the possibility to include heterogeneous agents and model policies. However, before the modeling process can begin, a thorough understanding of the context of the model and the stakeholders is needed. In the next chapter, an overview of the modeling context is provided.

2.2 Organization of Swiss Urban Drainage Management

The **Swiss law for water protection (GSchG)** is based on the 'polluter pays' principle. As municipalities are the smallest political entities in Switzerland, they are generally responsible for the economically efficient operation of urban drainage and wastewater treatment in their territory. They are required to draw up a **GEP**¹ according to the requirements of the canton [Maurer, 2012].

Typical organizational structures

The smallest functional entity of wastewater management is the catchment area of a WWTP. If the catchment area involves several municipalities, the operation of the common WWTP is organized through contracts or, in most cases, through a wastewater association. Two typical cases are distinguished [VSA, 2009]:

Case 1 The entire wastewater treatment and urban drainage infrastructure is owned and operated by a single organization. The organization can be...

Case 1A: ...a single municipality, if its territory extends over the entire WWTP catchment area.

Case 1B: ...a wastewater association, private or municipal organization, if the catchment area involves several municipalities

Case 2: The WWTP is operated by a single organization (e.g. a wastewater association, private or municipal organization), while each municipality owns and operates the urban drainage in its area.

The two cases are illustrated in Figure 2.1. Case 1 (A and B) is most efficient and permits the use of synergies, because organizational obstacles for infrastructure operation are more likely to be absent. Especially in catchment areas fragmented into small municipalities, the benefits of this organizational form are large. Case 2 involves more coordination effort which has to be justified within the GEP. Intermediate cases exist, where e.g. urban drainage infrastructure is owned by the municipality but operated by the association. A third case, where each municipality owns and operates its own urban drainage system without coordination with the WWTP operator, is explicitly discouraged, but is still practiced in some catchment areas [VSA, 2009]. The organization of urban drainage plays a crucial role for the measurement of CSOs, as the WWTP operators are experienced with the use of measurement data, while this is not always the case for the responsible

¹ *Generelle Entwässerungsplanung* - GEP is a planning instrument concerning urban drainage, which involves stakeholders from the municipality, the WWTP operator, the cantonal authority, and a planning engineer in a continuous process.

persons in the municipalities or sewer operators.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of different operation and ownership situations.

It is not exactly known, how many municipalities organize their wastewater treatment and urban drainage management according to which of the two typical cases. In a survey among Swiss municipalities from 2017 [Ladner, 2017], 903 of the municipality officials claimed that the municipality organizes wastewater / urban drainage on its own, while 823 of them are organized in some form of collaboration with other municipalities or private providers².

2.3 Agent-Based Model for Sensor Adoption

In this section, the developed prototype is described. First, the stakeholders from the real-world (Figure B.3 in the appendix) are introduced and simplified to agents in the prototype (Figure 2.3). Afterwards, the theoretical concepts governing the agent behavior and opinion dynamics are introduced, followed by an overview of the model's structure and parameters. The next subsection describes how the parameters are generated from survey data. Finally, the last subsection describes how the agents' social network is constructed from geodata. An overview of the model can be found in Figure 2.2.

Only sensor adoption is modeled. Even though the current question might concern rather the management of measurement data than the adoption of sensors, we focus on the latter in this prototype. This decision was taken because sensor adoption is the first necessary step to obtain monitoring data from CSOs. Without monitoring data, no data management is possible. If 'sensor adoption' is referred to in this Master's thesis, it relates to the installation of a water level meter in a CSO tank. The specific target of the prototype is to model the sensor adoption in CSO tanks over time. As no distinct data about the operation and ownership of CSO tanks is readily available (except for the canton of Bern, see Appendix B), we focus on the decision of the agents to adopt a sensor. The stakeholders that take the decision to adopt sensors are assumed to be either the municipalities or the WWTP operators, which are introduced in the next subsection. Thus, the most important output of the prototype is the share of these two agent types that adopt sensors over time, while the share is treated separately for each agent type. Furthermore, other states of the model will also be analyzed in this model, such as the trajectories of the attitudes of the agents (Subsection 2.3.2).

²Not for all of the 2255 municipalities in the survey, there is a reply. Unfortunately, the survey question did not differentiate between wastewater treatment and urban drainage management. In Figure B.2 in the appendix, a more detailed evaluation of the survey results is shown.

Figure 2.2: An overview of the model with annotated section numbers.

2.3.1 Simplification of the Stakeholders

In order to implement the model on a computer, the complex reality has to be broken down. In the prototype, four different types of stakeholders are included, namely the WWTP operator, the cantonal authority, the municipality, and the engineer. These stakeholders were determined based on expert knowledge³ and on the availability of geo-spatial data to generate agents. The focus lies on the inter-communal and inter-catchment area level. As geo-spatial data is available for the whole of Switzerland, agents are generated for all 26 cantons. Furthermore, survey data is available for wastewater associations and cantonal authorities. The option of modelling on a smaller scale (municipality or catchment area) was considered, but discarded due to the lack of fine-grained data about stakeholders. The amount of generated agents for each type is listed in Table 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Simplified stakeholders of CSOs in Switzerland.

The WWTP operator is considered a key actor in our model because the use of a water level meter in a CSO tank, connected to the process control system of the WWTP, can be beneficial for the operation of the WWTP and the operator's system knowledge. In this case, the simplification consists of aggregating all stakeholders connected to the WWTP, such as the wastewater association and the infrastructure operator itself. For our model, we consider that every WWTP in Data Set C.1.4 represents a WWTP operator.

Previous studies on **cantonal authorities** [Manny, 2017] provide useful data on their role in the sensor adoption process. From a semi-structured survey and face-to-face interviews, the cantonal

³Liliane Manny, Jörg Rieckermann

authorities are characterized concerning, their motivation and problem recognition (see Subsection 2.3.5). The cantonal authority plays a central role in Swiss urban drainage management, as it is responsible for the enforcement of the surface water protection law (GSchG). Although in larger cantons, the responsibilities for municipalities in different regions may be divided among several people, only one authority per canton is included in the model.

As for the WWTP operator agent, several actors are aggregated to a single one for the **municipalities**. Usually, the involved stakeholders related to the municipality include the building authority, the municipality engineer, and members of the municipal council [Baudirektion Kanton Zürich, 2015]. However, further stakeholders can be involved, related to e.g. environmental protection, agriculture, water supply, and fire department. In total, 2215 municipality agents are created for Switzerland.

The GEP engineering consultant is crucial in the process of drawing up a GEP, having the knowledge of the current state of technology. The **engineer** agent can be compared to an super-regional engineering company. In the model, five equally important engineer agents are included. In reality, more and not only large companies are involved in the planning of a GEP.

2.3.2 Behavior Model

The central question regarding the agents⁴ in this ABM prototype is: How does the agent decide whether to adopt a sensor in the CSO tank or not? To model an agents' 'inner' processes that influence sensor adoption, a behavior model has to be established. The following subsection describes how the psychological aspects that lead to a certain behavior can be taken into account in the ABM prototype.

Behavior Models in ABM

In a selection of eight recent ABMs for adoption of photo-voltaic technology [Caprioli et al., 2020], the Theory of Planned behavior (TPB) [Ajzen, 1991] is used along with the Relative Agreement Algorithm (Subsection 2.3.3) in around half of the cases. TPB is not always applied in the same manner, but sometimes extended [Kasargodu Anebagilu et al., 2021] or reduced. Other methods for behavioral models include financial evaluations, logistic regressions, utility functions and adoption probability levels. Earlier on in the prototype development, decision trees and probabilistic behavior of agents were considered (See appendix H).

Theory of Planned Behavior

TPB is a widely used framework and applied e.g. in the domain of health, marketing, or environmental psychology. TPB is centered around a single, well specified behavior, that is either performed or not, depending on the intention of a person to perform this behavior. According to TPB, the intention to perform a certain behaviour is composed of three factors: the individual's personal attitude towards the behavior, the subjective norm and the perceived behavioral control (Figure 2.4). Firstly, the individual's attitude describes its personal feelings towards the behavior. Secondly, the normative beliefs and subjective norm describe the individual's belief of what society and relevant others (friends, family, spouse, etc), respectively, think about the behavior. Finally, the perceived behavioral control is the individual's perception of how easy or difficult it is to perform the behavior. If the intention resulting from these three factors sufficient, the individual will display the behavior, unless it is moderated by the perceived behavioural control. In the application of TPB, several empirical weights have to be derived from survey data, that determine the importance of each factor.

TPB in the Prototype

Following the methodology suggested by Rai and Robinson (2015), a simplified version of TPB is used in this master thesis. The right hand side of Figure 2.4 shows the simplification of TPB that is used for the prototype. For each agent, the attitude towards the behavior and the subjective norm are combined to the variable *sia* (sensor installation attitude). Furthermore, each agent obtains a variable *pbc* signifying the perceived behavioral control. The agent adopts a sensor if both, the

⁴Only municipalities and WWTP operators adopt sensors.

Figure 2.4: Original and simplified schema for TPB. The schema on the left was adapted from [Ajzen, 2013]. The simplification of TPB for the prototype consists in combining the factors 'attitude' and 'subjective norm' to a single variable sia and removing the influence of the perceived behavioral control pbc on the intention. The behavior is performed if $sia > sia_threshold$ and $pbc > pbc_threshold$

values of sia and pbc , are above a certain threshold, $sia_threshold$ and $pbc_threshold$, respectively.

The initial values of the agent variables are calculated from the survey among wastewater associations and cantonal authorities as described in Subsection 2.3.5. An estimate for sia is calculated by taking into account the factors *know-how*, *vision of the future*, and *social influence*. The value for pbc results from survey questions concerning organizational and operational aspects. While each agent keeps the same value of pbc for the entire simulation period, sia will be 'traded' during interactions among agents. This process is described in the next subsection.

2.3.3 Opinion Dynamics

To simulate the interactions among the agents over time, the **Relative Agreement (RA) Algorithm** [Deffuant et al., 2002, Hegselmann and Krause, 2002, Meadows and Cliff, 2012] is used. The RA algorithm assumes 'bounded confidence' of an agent towards the opinion of its peers. Whenever two agents interact with each other, an agent will only be influenced by another agent, whose opinion lies within a span (\pm uncertainty u) from its own opinion. After the interaction, the influenced agent updates its opinion (sia) and uncertainty proportional to the relative agreement of the two agents and a factor μ , which determines the weight of interaction. The interactions happen each time step, which allows to observe the evolution of the agents' opinions. A detailed description of the algorithm is provided in Appendix E.

The RA Algorithm is driven by each agent's value of sia and u that vary constantly during the simulation period. While sia results from TPB, there is no clear indication on the value for u . [Rai and Robinson, 2015] assign the value of u according to the inverse absolute value of sia due to behavioral research that suggests that the uncertainty is smaller for extreme opinions [Maio et al., 1996]. In our case, the value of sia being set between 0 and 1, this reasoning results in the following equation:

$$u = 0.51 - |sia - 0.5| \quad (2.1)$$

A small value of 0.01 is added to u to prevent it from being equal to 0. However, [Caprioli et al., 2020] initialize the agents' uncertainty in a random manner. Thus, this possibility will also be considered in Section 2.5 to assess the impact of assumption concerning the assignment of u .

Social network

The agents only exchange their opinions with agents they are connected to via links on a social network. How this network is constructed is described in Section 2.3.6.

Communication schedule

Not all agent types are assumed to communicate at the same rate with other agent types. E.g. a municipality communicates less frequently with other municipalities than with the operator of the connected WWTP. Thus, a communication schedule is introduced in the form of a symmetric matrix (see Appendix F). The values in the matrix describe the number of time steps that occur between the interactions of two agent types. The model proceeds in time steps of one month, thus two agents can at most have 12 interactions per year. Each time step, each agent communicates with each neighboring agent connected to it through the social network among the agents. This makes the opinion exchange deterministic rather than stochastic, which simplifies the analysis of the model.

How a single agent behaves based on the concepts for behavior and opinion dynamics is illustrated in Figure 2.5. In the following subsection, an overview over the input parameters of the model is given, followed by how they are derived from empirical data and prior knowledge.

2.3.4 Model Input

The input of the prototype can be distinguished into three groups: structural parameters (S), model parameters (M), and agent parameters (A). As described in Subsection 2.3, the output (Y) of the prototype are the share of agents with sensors of the WWTP operators and municipalities over time, respectively. The model can be described by the following function:

$$Y = f(S, M, A) \quad (2.2)$$

The parameter groups are subdivided into several parameters each, which are listed below:

S Structural parameters

- Graph: Social network of the agents. Subsection 2.3.6 is dedicated to how the links between the agents are generated from geo-spatial data sets.
- Communication schedule: Defines the interaction between agents of certain types. The frequency of interactions between different agent types, e.g. a municipality and a cantonal authority, is estimated by experts (see Appendix F).

These 'parameters' can rather be seen configurations than values. They determine which agent communicates with which other agent, how much and when. The impact of these 'parameters' is assessed through numerical experiments, as described in Subsection 2.6.1.

M Model parameters

- sia_threshold*: Opinion threshold above which the agent adopts a sensor. Stays constant over the entire simulation period.
- pbc_threshold*: Perceived behavioural control threshold above which the agent adopts a sensor. Usually stays constant over the entire simulation period, but may be decreased over time for simulation of policies.
- μ : Exchange rate of opinions from the RA algorithm. Stays constant over the entire simulation period.

These parameters should be adjusted using empirical data, if possible. A sensitivity analysis is performed on these parameters (see Subsection 2.6.2).

A Agent parameters

- sia*: Attitude of the agent that is altered through opinion dynamics.
- pbc*: Perceived behavioural control, stays constant over the simulation period.

Figure 2.5: Flowchart of the model describing the behavior of each agent. After the agents are initialized with the variables *sia*, *pbc*, and *u*, the RA Algorithm proceeds each time step and the agents modify each others values for *sia* and *u*, as it is illustrated in Figure 2.5. The chosen time step is one month. If an agent’s *sia* crosses the attitude threshold *sia_threshold* while the agent’s *pbc* is above the *pbc_threshold*, the agent adopts a sensor. Only municipalities and WWTP operators are considered to adopt sensors. The other agent types only participate in the exchange of *sia*. The communication between agent types is determined through the communication schedule.

<i>u</i> :	Uncertainty of the agent that is altered through opinion dynamics.
<i>sensor_adopted</i> :	If a sensor is adopted or not. Is changed to from <i>False</i> to <i>True</i> if <i>sia</i> > <i>sia_threshold</i> and <i>pbc</i> > <i>pbc_threshold</i> .

For each of the parameters above, usually a vector of 2966 initial values is given, corresponding to the number of agents modeled for Switzerland (see Table 2.3). These values then change over the course of the simulation period. Sensitivity analysis of these parameters is performed by varying the entire distribution they are sampled from (see Subsection 2.6.2). How these values are initialized from prior knowledge and empirical data is described in the next section.

2.3.5 Agent Parameters from Prior Knowledge

The initial parameters of the agents are estimated from the survey among cantonal authorities and wastewater associations. Where no survey data is available, the parameter values rely on the estimations of experts. For the relative agreement algorithm, the parameters *sia* (attitude) and *u* (uncertainty) are needed for each agent individually. Relevant for sensor adoption in the model are also *pbc* (perceived behavioural control) and *sensor_adopted*.

WWTP Operators

For the initial parameters of the WWTP operator agent, it is assumed that the wastewater associations are representative of all WWTP operators, including municipalities that operate their own WWTP. Table 2.1 shows how *sia* of the WWTP operator agent is estimated. The attitude *sia* is constructed from the parameters *know-how*, *vision* and *social influence*, which are calculated from the survey among wastewater associations. In Table 2.2, the factors taken into account for the calculation of *pbc* are listed. As described in Subsection 2.3.3, the opinion uncertainty *u* is assigned to the agents either randomly or inversely proportional to the extremity of the opinion *sia*. Please find a more detailed description of the calculation of initial parameters in Appendix D.

Figure 2.6 shows *sia* and *pbc* calculated for the respondents of the wastewater association survey. It is noted that only 8 of 70 respondents do not have any sensors adopted in CSO tanks, half of which are not operating any CSO tanks. According to the survey among cantonal authorities, combined with the geographical location of the survey WWTPs, around 1 out of 3 wastewater associations have no sensors adopted¹.

There is no correlation of WWTP size and attitude. As the WWTPs from the survey were matched to the geo-spatial data set with information about WWTPs, further analysis was performed with the aim to find a correlation between *sia* and *pbc* (from survey) and attributes of the geo-spatial data set (e.g. size). This could allow for an extrapolation of *sia/pbc* to all 720 WWTPs in the geo-spatial data set. However, no such correlation could be found. Further details can be found in the appendix (Figure D.2).

The assignment of donors to WWTPs from geodata.

As input for the model, *sia*, *pbc*, and *u* are needed. For each of the 720 WWTPs from the geo-spatial data set, a so-called donor from the survey respondents is sampled to provide *sia* and *pbc*⁵. From the survey among cantonal authorities, an estimation of the share of wastewater associations with sensors in CSO tanks is given. Depending on which canton the WWTP lies in and the share of wastewater associations with sensors in this canton, the donor is either chosen from the survey respondents with or without sensors, respectively. As no correlation could be found between *sia/pbc* and WWTP size, the donors were chosen at random. The probability which distribution is chosen is equal to the estimated share of associations with or without sensors, respectively. Afterwards, the donor's *sia* and *pbc* are varied randomly within 10% of their respective ranges to smoothen the distribution of values. The resulting parameters are shown on the left hand side of Figure 2.7.

¹Assumption: All WWTPs in the respective canton are operated by wastewater associations.

Table 2.1: Calculation of *sia* from wastewater association survey. In the column 'weighting' the cursive words designate the quantity given in the 'quantity' column. For further information, see Appendix D.

parameter	quantity	question	weighting
Know-how	CSO tanks with sensors [#]	14	$0.117 * \log(1 + rbmess)$
	sensors in sewers [#]	15	$0.059 * \log(1 + kanalmess)$
	rain meters [#]	16	$0.059 * \log(1 + rainmess)$
	flow to wwtp measured [bool]	17.1	$0.117 * rbq$
	water level measured [bool]	17.2	$0.117 * rbh$
	CSO duration measured [bool]	17.3	$0.117 * rbt$
	CSO frequency measured [bool]	17.4	$0.117 * rbn$
	CSO amount measured [bool]	17.5	$0.117 * rbv$
	water level in sewer measured [bool]	18.1	$0.059 * kanalh$
	flow in sewer measured [bool]	18.2	$0.059 * kanalq$
water quality in sewer measured [bool]	18.3	$0.059 * kanalquali$	
Vision	agreement vision RTC	35	yes: 0.25, on condition: 0.125
	infrastructure operated besides wwtp	36	CSOs only: 0.25, CSOs & sewage: 0.125
Social influence	Motivation from cantonal authority [1-10]	[1]	$\frac{0.5 * kkz}{100} * \frac{motivation}{10}$
	Cooperation with cantonal authority [%]	33	
	Participation in events [bool]	34	$0.5 * fc$

[1] assessment by Liliane Manny

Table 2.2: Calculation of *pbc* from wastewater association survey

parameter	quantity	question	weighting
pbc	Freedom of decision [%]	5.1	$0.167 * avfreie/100$
	Financial freedom [%]	5.2	$0.167 * avfreif/100$
	Ownership of CSO tanks [bool]	8.2	$0.167 * oerb$
	Operated CSO tanks [#]	9	$0.167 * \log(1 + rb)$
	Renovation of CSO tanks within the next 5 years [bool]	11	$0.167 * rbfutur$
	Know-how	[1]	$0.167 * know - how$
	Operates CSO tanks [bool]	8.1 & 9	if obara \neq 1 or rb>0 [2]

[1] calculated according to Table 2.1

[2] multiplied with all the above

Figure 2.6: The parameters *sia* and *pbc* of the evaluated survey respondents (wastewater associations)

Cantonal Authorities

The initialization parameters for the cantonal authority are estimated using the assessment of the cantonal authorities attitudes in the following domains [Manny, 2017]:

- Problem recognition
- Usefulness of sensor technology
- Motivation towards municipalities and wastewater associations
- Using sensor data for compliance assessment

Concerning each of these domains, the cantonal authorities' attitudes were rated between 1 and 10. The average of all 4 items was used to calculate *sia*. Subsequently, it was normalized to the span from 0 to 1 in accordance with *sia* of the WWTP operators. For 5 cantons, no assessment was available. In these cases, the average of the corresponding value of the other cantonal authorities was used. Since the cantonal authorities do not adopt sensors, only the parameters relevant to the RA algorithm are needed. Thus, *pbc* is set to 0. The uncertainty *u* is assigned according to Equation (2.1). The resulting values are shown on the right hand side of Figure 2.7.

Municipalities and Engineers

As survey data from these agents are lacking, we rely on the estimation of experts for these parameters. *sia* and *pbc* were sampled from two distributions (see Appendix F.1 and G.2). While the *sia* of engineers was assumed to be rather high, *sia* and *pbc* were considered to be low.

2.3.6 The Stakeholders' Social Network

As there is no detailed information available as to the supposedly highly diverse relationships between the stakeholders throughout the whole of Switzerland, the structure social network between stakeholders relies on the following assumptions:

Figure 2.7: The parameters sia , pbc , and u for WWTP operators and cantonal authorities.

- The WWTP operators communicate with other WWTP operators whose catchment areas are adjacent to theirs.
- The WWTP operators communicate with municipalities whose territory overlaps with the catchment area.
- The WWTP operators communicate with the cantonal authority of the canton the WWTP is situated in.
- The municipalities communicate with the cantonal authority of the canton it belongs to.
- The municipalities communicate with adjacent municipalities.
- The cantonal authorities communicate with other cantonal authorities of adjacent cantons.
- Every municipality communicates with one of the engineers chosen at random.
- Every WWTP operator communicates with one of the engineers chosen at random.
- Every cantonal authority communicates with every engineer.
- Every engineer communicates with all other engineers.

Furthermore, agents communicate on a local level, as is it also assumed for generating social networks in other ABMs[Rai and Robinson, 2015]. Using the above assumptions and the geo-spatial data sets for canton, municipality, and catchment area boundaries ⁶, a social network is

⁶Sources: see Appendix C

obtained. The amount of links in the generated network is shown in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: The number of agents and links between them in the generated network of Switzerland

	Agents	Links			
		WWTP operator	Municipality	Cantonal authority	Engineer
WWTP operator	720	1771	2504	720	720
Municipality	2215	-	6486	2215	2215
Cantonal authority	26	-	-	57	130
Engineer	5	-	-	-	10
Total	2966	16828			

2.4 Plausibility

Efforts were undertaken to obtain data that can serve for comparison of the model output⁷ to reality. We searched for data about sensors installed in CSOs, ideally containing the time of installation. However, data suitable for the comparison to the model output could be found. Nevertheless, a novel data set was obtained from the automation company Chestonag (Appendix C.1.3), containing the number of external infrastructure elements⁸ of WWTPs.

Rule-Catalog

In the ABM suggested by Tillman (2001), the interactions among agents are governed by a rule-catalog. The rule-catalog contains a list of assumptions on the behavior of agents in the form of if-then-rules for the behavior of stakeholders. The rule-catalog is presented to a group of experts who can either agree completely, partly, or not at all with each rule. Iteratively, the rule-catalog is improved until the experts agree at least partly with the rules. Before the introduction of TPB as behavior model into the ABM prototype, efforts were undertaken to establish a rule-catalog (see Appendix H for more details).

Expert Consultation

Even though the rule-catalog was not used to model agent behavior, it proved a useful tool for the communication with experts. The assumptions for the sensor adoption model and its configurations were listed in a questionnaire which was then presented to experts from the domain of urban drainage management (see Appendix I). Furthermore, the experts were asked for estimations that were used to adjust model parameters, e.g. the communication schedule. Through this process, we aim to improve the plausibility of the model regarding the domain of urban drainage management. In the responses to the questionnaire, the experts deemed the assumptions in the questionnaire to be at least partly true.

To characterize the uncertainties in the model, a sensitivity analysis is performed as described in Subsection 2.6.2. Furthermore, numerical experiments are performed to evaluate the model behaviour in different configurations (Subsection 2.6.1).

2.5 Scenarios

In this section, different scenarios are presented. These include the baseline Scenario (Subsection 2.5.1) and scenarios for policy evaluation (Subsection 2.5.2). An overview of the configurations can be found in Table 2.4, while a more detailed description of the scenarios and numerical experiments (Subsection 2.6.1) is provided in Appendix F.

⁷As described in Section 2.3, the model output is the share of agents by type that adopt sensors over time, while the attitudes *sia* of the agents are considered internal states of the model

⁸'Aussenbauwerke', e.g. pumping stations or CSO tanks

Table 2.4: Overview of scenarios and numerical experiments

	No.	Title	Changes with respect to baseline
Baseline Scenario	Sc. 0	Baseline for comparison	-
Numerical experiments	Exp. 1	Order of communication among agents	Shifted communication schedule
	Exp. 2	Input uncertainty	Communication schedule provided by a different expert
	Exp. 3	Network configuration	Fully connected graph as social network among cantonal authorities
	Exp. 4	Opinion dynamics	Random uncertainty of opinion
Scenarios for policy evaluation	Sc. 1	Influence of GEP-meetings	Less frequent communication among the stakeholders involved in the GEP
	Sc. 2	Regulation	Gradual increase of agents' <i>sia</i> if no sensor is adopted
	Sc. 3	Better technology	Gradual decrease of <i>pbcthreshold</i> to lower the barrier for technology adoption

2.5.1 Baseline Scenario

This scenario uses the best knowledge currently available. The WWTP operator and cantonal authority agents are initialized according to Subsection 2.3.5 based on survey data. The engineers and municipalities are initialized according to the responses of experts to the questionnaire mentioned in Section 2.4. Furthermore, the communication schedule was taken from the expert questionnaire under the assumption that GEP-meetings regularly take place. The stakeholders' social network was created as described in Section 2.3.6. The scenario serves as baseline for the comparison with numerical experiments and scenarios for policy evaluation. Furthermore, a basic sensitivity analysis is performed for the parameters that cannot be determined through empirical data with the aim to adjust them to reasonable values. More details on this process can be found in Appendix F.1.

2.5.2 The Impact of Selected Policies on Sensor Adoption

To demonstrate how policies can be incorporated into the prototype, three scenarios are run relating to policies. In Table 2.4, these listed together with the baseline scenario and numerical experiments (Subsection 2.6.1).

No GEP-Meeting - Scenario 1

From experts from cantonal authorities, we know that the GEP constitutes an important tool to promote sensor adoption and data management. During the process of drawing up or revising a GEP, the stakeholders engineer, municipality, and cantonal authority meet up regularly to discuss the future requirements and plans for urban drainage. As the baseline scenario assumes that a regular GEP-meeting takes place, Scenario 1 aims to simulate the opposite scenario where no GEP takes place, such that the influence of GEP-meetings can be assessed through comparison. In the model, the meetings among stakeholders are implemented through the communication schedule (Subsection 2.3.3). In Scenario 1, the frequency of meetings among the agent types municipality, cantonal authority, and engineer are reduced.

Regulation - Scenario 2

Recalling the Theory of Planned behavior (Figure 2.4), it can be argued that a regulation impacts the normative beliefs of an agent. Regarding the simplifications made for the prototype, stronger normative beliefs correspond to an increase of the parameter *sia* of an agent. In our case, a regulation that requires that every CSO tank is equipped with a sensor would increase the pressure on an agent to comply with the regulation. In the model, this is implemented by gradually raising *sia* of the agents with no sensor adopted after the introduction of a regulation. In Scenario 2, these agent's *sia* is raised by 0.01 every time step between 2020 and 2022. Please note that by how much the agents' attitude is increased is an arbitrary value.

Better Technology - Scenario 3

An improvement of measurement technology will lower an agent's barrier to adopt a sensor. In the context of TPB, this is implemented by lowering *pbcthreshold*. As the improvement of technology is assumed to happen over time, *pbcthreshold* is reduced by a small amount every time step, such that the *pbcthreshold* reaches 0 at the end of the simulation period.

2.6 Analysis of the Prototype

To analyze the prototype's behavior with respect to the input parameters, a sensitivity analysis is performed (Subsection 2.6.2). However, not all uncertainties depend on the input parameters, but rather on the internal structure of the model. In ABM, these uncertainties can be addressed through the method of 'robustness analysis' [Grimm and Berger, 2016], consisting in altering the internal model structure, depending on the individual model. Such a 'robustness analysis' through numerical experiments is described in the next subsection.

2.6.1 Numerical Experiments

The 'numerical experiments' are used to explore the model behavior rather than for the assessment of an imaginable future scenario or a policy. The following numerical experiments are performed:

- Exp. 1 is used to assess the impact of a different sequence of opinion exchange among the agents.
- Exp. 2 explores the impact of different perspectives onto the model output by using a second plausible communication schedule provided by a different expert than in the baseline scenario.
- Exp. 3 evaluates the impact of social networks structure by assuming that the cantonal authorities are not only locally connected, but each authority to every other one.
- Exp. 4 explores an uncertainty inherent to the opinion dynamic model, namely the assignment of opinion uncertainty u to the agents.

A more detailed description of the numerical experiments can be found in Appendix F.

2.6.2 Sensitivity Analysis

For the sensitivity analysis of the prototype, the Morris method [Morris, 1991, Campolongo et al., 2007] is used to screen the parameter space. This One-at-a-time (OAT) method is well suited for the sensitivity analysis of ABMs, as it is a relatively straightforward method and yields insight into model behaviour. Especially in the case of a computationally intensive ABM prototype, the Morris screening method is suitable, being relatively cheap in terms of computational cost. At this stage of modelling, the focus lies on uncovering qualitatively the most important input parameters, which may even be done without explicitly calculating the partial derivatives with respect to the input parameters for ABMs [ten Broeke et al., 2016]. Next to the Morris method, a 'Sobol' sensitivity analysis [Saltelli, 2000] was implemented at an earlier stage of the model. However, due to the high computation cost and time reasons, it was not performed on the full model.

A simple sensitivity analysis can be performed for the model parameters *sia_threshold*, *pbc_threshold*, and μ , as their value can easily be varied for the entire model.⁹ However, the structural parameters, such as the social network and communication schedule, as well as the agent parameters, are less straightforward. The structural parameters are analyzed through a 'robustness' rather than a sensitivity analysis, as described in the previous section. For the sensitivity analysis of the ABM prototype, not every single agent's parameters will be investigated individually. Instead, groups of agent parameters will be varied one-at-a-time. The output on which the sensitivity analysis is performed are the shares of WWTP operators or municipalities that have sensors adopted.

Agent Parameters to Model Parameters

The grouping of agent parameters is addressed by sampling them from distributions and then varying the mean of the distribution during the sensitivity analysis. A more detailed explanation of this process can be found in Appendix G. This way, agent parameters are transformed into model parameters and be treated the same way as e.g. *sia_threshold*. How the parameter range was determined, can also be found in Appendix G.

2.6.3 Implementation

Model

The implementation of the ABM prototype in Python can be divided into three parts. The first one has the aim to load the data, analyze it, and plot the analysis of the individual or combined data sets. To achieve this, mainly the **pandas** and **geopandas** packages are used. At the end of this part, the social network of agents is available and the agents, for which data is available, have been prepared according to the next subsection. The second part contains the implementation of the dynamic part of the model (Figure 2.5). This part was developed using the **mesa** framework for ABM. Finally, the third part of the implementation contains scripts for running the model in different configurations, sensitivity analysis and plotting of the results.

Opinion dynamics

For the opinion exchange, we assume that every opinion exchange between two agents happens in both directions simultaneously. During the initialization of the model, the network is transformed into a bidirectional graph. The graph serves as the environment, through which the agents communicate. Each agent has a 'letterbox' (a directional link) for each other agent it is connected to. To this link, the attributes *sia* and *u* (Subsection 2.3.5) are assigned and read out in the following time step by the receiving agent. The social network is described in Subsection 2.3.6.

Sensitivity Analysis

The sensitivity analysis was implemented using the Morris package from the **SALib** library for Python [Herman and Usher, 2017]. The Morris package's sample function generates parameter combinations within the specified bounds, which are then used as input parameters for the model. While the model is run for each parameter, the trajectories of the model and agent variables are saved. Finally, the sensitivity analysis can be performed for different metrics without rerunning the entire model. Running a single model iteration takes around 45 seconds.

⁹See Subsection 2.3.4 for an overview.

3 Results

In this Section, the simulation results are shown. All numerical experiments and scenarios were performed over a simulation period of 10 years. First, the baseline scenario, followed by the scenarios for policy evaluation. Then, the results of the numerical experiments are included. An overview of the results for municipalities can be found in Figure 3.1. Finally, the results from the sensitivity analysis are presented.

Figure 3.1: Overview of all scenarios and numerical experiments. The share of municipalities after a 10 years simulation period, 100 iterations each scenario / numerical experiment. Notable is Exp. 4, where the results show a wider variation due to the random assignment of the uncertainty u . Sc. 2 shows the highest share of agents with sensors. Figure F.1 in the appendix is the corresponding plot for the WWTP operators.

3.1 Scenarios

3.1.1 Baseline Scenario

In Figure 3.2, the baseline scenario is shown with varying μ . A higher value of μ goes along with a faster opinion exchange and a faster increase of the share of agents with sensors. However, the curves converge at the end of the simulation period such that there is only a small difference in the share of agents with sensors for all values of μ . For the parameters $pb_{c_threshold}$ and $sia_threshold$, similar figures can be found in Appendix F.1.

Figure 3.2: The share of WWTP operators with sensors over the simulation period of 10 years in the baseline scenario, while the parameter μ is varied. (Average of 20 runs for each value). It can be seen that with a higher value of μ , the sensor adoption rate is higher at the beginning of the simulation period.

3.1.2 Scenarios for Policy Evaluation

In Figure 3.3, the share of WWTP operators and Municipalities with sensors over time can be found for the Scenarios 1, 2, and 3. Comparing the baseline (Sc. 0) and the scenario with reduced communication among the agents involved in the GEP (Sc. 1), almost no difference can be seen for the WWTP operators, among which approximately 75% have adopted sensors at the end of the 10-year simulation period. Among the municipalities, the share of agents with sensors is around 2% lower, in the scenario without GEP (Sc. 1) than in the baseline (Sc. 0) by the end of the simulation period, which corresponds to value of around 23% (Sc. 1) and 25% in the baseline, respectively.

In both, the scenario with a regulation (Sc. 2) and better technology (Sc. 3), an increase of the share of agents with sensors can be seen in comparison with the baseline. For the WWTP operators, both scenarios reach a value of 78%. In the 'better technology' scenario, the share of municipalities with sensors shows a moderate increase by around 1% with respect to the baseline. However, the 'regulation' scenario stands out. Here, a fast and strong increase can be observed for the share of municipalities with sensors between years 2020 and 2022, when the regulation is introduced. As to the share of municipalities with sensors over time, it can be seen in Figure 3.3 that the regulation has by far the largest effect on sensor adoption, rising the share of municipalities with sensors from 23% to 81% with respect to the baseline. A plot illustrating the opinion dynamics for the 'regulation' scenario can be found in the appendix in Figure F.5.

Figure 3.3: Results of the scenarios for policy evaluation described in Table 2.4. The scenario ‘regulation’ shows the largest increase concerning the shares of agents with sensors. (Average of 100 runs for each scenario)

3.2 Analysis of the Prototype

3.2.1 Numerical Experiments

In Figure 3.4, the results of the numerical experiments can be found. Concerning the share of WWTP operators with sensors, all the numerical experiments lead to similar trajectories that approach a value of 75% at the end of the simulation period. While most numerical experiments converge to a share of municipalities with sensors of 25%, it is noted that an average value of 28% is attained by the numerical experiment where the opinion uncertainty is assigned randomly to the agents (Exp. 4).

To illustrate the opinion dynamics, the trajectories of agent opinions are shown in Figure 3.5 and 3.6. The two figures display the opinions of the agents in eastern Switzerland with opinion uncertainty u assigned according to the baseline scenario and randomly as in Exp. 4. With smaller u for extreme values of sia (Figure 3.5), the agents’ opinions tend to polarize. For a random assignment of u (Figure 3.6), the opinions tend to converge at more intermediate values.

3.2.2 Sensitivity Analysis

In Figure 3.7 and 3.8, the results of the Morris-screening method are shown. The two plots in Figure 3.7 illustrate the influence of the different entry parameters on the total share of Municipalities with sensors at the end of a simulation period of 10 years (120 time steps). It is noted that the highest influence is assigned to the mean of the distribution from which the municipalities’ sia

Figure 3.4: Results of the numerical experiments described in Table 2.4. Compared to the other numerical experiments, a notable increase in Exp. 4 'opinion dynamics' can be seen. (Average of 100 runs for each numerical experiment)

and pb_c are drawn. The second most important parameter is the initial share of municipalities with sensors, followed by $sia_threshold$ and the distribution shape of the WWTP operators with sensors. In the co-variance plot, the absolute value of the influence is shown, e.g. an increase of $sia_threshold$ leads to a smaller share of WWTPs with sensors. In Appendix G, the full results of the model runs can be found for this metric.

Figure 3.8 shows the co-variance plots of a different metric, namely the share of WWTP operators that adopt sensors during the simulation period. As in Figure 3.7, the initial distribution of sia and pb_c plays the most important role. Here, however, it is the initial distribution of WWTP operators. In comparison to 3.7, the initial share of agents with sensors play a smaller role than $sia_threshold$. More results and different metrics can be found in Appendix G.

Figure 3.5: Opinion dynamics including 482 agents (eastern Switzerland) - uncertainty u was assigned inverse proportionally to the extremity of the opinion ($u = 0.51 - |sia - 0.5|$). A polarization is observed.

Figure 3.6: Opinion dynamics including 482 agents (eastern Switzerland) - uncertainty u was assigned randomly (0.01-1). The agents' attitudes converge at intermediate values.

Figure 3.7: Morris screening co-variance plot for the total of Municipalities with sensors in 2027 (after 120 timesteps of 1 month), 600 iterations total for the whole of Switzerland. In the plot on the left, the values for the absolute value of the mean μ^* and standard deviation σ are shown. In the scatter plot on the right, the relation between μ^* and σ is illustrated. The farther from the origin a point is, the higher the influence of the parameter.

Figure 3.8: Morris screening co-variance plot for the increase of WWTP operators with sensors from 2017 to 2027, 600 iterations total for the whole of Switzerland. In the plot on the left, the values for the absolute value of the mean μ^* and standard deviation σ are shown. In the scatter plot on the right, the relation between μ^* and σ is illustrated. The farther from the origin a point is, the higher the influence of the parameter.

4 Discussion

In this chapter, first the results from scenarios and numerical experiments are discussed and general tendencies are analyzed. At the example of the baseline scenario, the parameter adjustment is discussed. Afterwards, the results of the policy evaluation are compared to results from the survey among wastewater associations [Manny, 2017]. Then, the uncertainties of the prototype are analyzed regarding numerical experiments and sensitivity analysis, as well as the method of TPB. Furthermore, the plausibility of the prototype is discussed regarding the assessment through experts and validation through empirical data. Finally, the approach of ABM is discussed in general, followed by a short section about the implementation.

4.1 Scenarios

In general, one could expect that the shares of agents with sensors steadily increase over time. However, in all scenarios (Figure 3.3), as well as numerical experiments (Figure 3.3), a 'saturation' can be observed towards the end of the simulation period, where almost no sensors are adopted anymore. This contradicts the expectations of the consulted experts in this domain. The reasons for this phenomenon lie in the structure of the model. Before the simulation period starts, all agents are initialized with a certain attitude. This attitude is iteratively 'traded' with the neighboring agents in the RA Algorithm. In an interaction between two agents either approaches their attitudes or does not take place, if the agents' attitudes are too far apart. Over time, this process leads to the convergence of attitudes. Furthermore, it can be observed that the attitudes (*sia*) of agents can decrease again, even after a sensor is adopted, which in turn influences other agents. In reality, stakeholders are assumed to draw a benefit from adopting sensors, which is important to convince municipalities to adopt sensors in CSO tanks according to an expert from urban drainage management. Thus, the introduction of a factor which increases *sia* over time after an agent adopted a sensor is to consider in a further development of the prototype, preferably coupled with an investigation of this phenomenon through psychological methods. This 'saturation' inherent in the structure of the model, next to the uncertainties concerning parameter values, is the reason why no long time periods can be simulated, e.g. over a span of 50 years starting in the 1970s, when the first sensors were adopted.

4.1.1 Baseline Scenario and Parameter Adjustment

The baseline scenario integrates the best of our knowledge, which is, however, not enough to determine parameter values with certainty. Due to a lack of empirical data, such as a time series of the amount of sensors adopted over time, several parameters have to be chosen ad hoc. For this prototype, this applies to the model parameters μ , *sia_threshold*, and *pbc_threshold*, as well as the distributions, from which *pbc* and *sia* for the engineers and municipalities were sampled. Figure 3.2, as well as Figures F.2, F.3, and F.4 in the appendix, show the baseline scenario while varying single parameters. These parameters can have a significant impact on the share of agents with sensors at the end of the simulation period but also on the shape of the curve. For low values of *sia_threshold*, a 'jump' can be observed in the first time step, where agents initialized with a value of *sia* higher than *sia_threshold* adopt sensors. The exact value for *sia_threshold* cannot be determined, as the agents' initial distributions of *sia* with or without sensors, respectively, overlap. The reasons for this lie in the application of TPB and will be discussed in Subsection 4.3.1.

4.1.2 Scenarios for Policy Evaluation

The results suggest that a policy addressing the municipalities or WWTP operators in charge of CSO tanks, such as a regulation, would be most effective compared to other scenarios with implemented policies. Furthermore, a frequent exchange among the stakeholders (GEP) accelerates the adoption of sensors, and so does the introduction of better technology. However, these results have to be handled with care, as the parameters were chosen ad hoc, e.g. the increase of *sia* and

its duration for the regulation scenario. The modeled policies have the aim to demonstrate the levers that can be used for policy evaluation. While the 'no GEP' Scenario applies changes to the communication schedule, the 'regulation' and 'better technology' Scenario targets the variables of TPB. However, it is not clear, how much exactly a regulation or better technology would impact a stakeholder in reality. This question enters the domain of psychology (see Subsection 4.3.1).

Comparison to Survey [Manny, 2017]

The five most effective policies instruments according to the survey conducted among cantonal authorities and wastewater associations (see Figure B.6 in the Appendix) are listed in the following. They are compared to the results from the prototype (Figure 3.3) and their (possible) incorporation in the prototype is discussed.

- Targets (data): As the prototype is for sensor adoption and not data management, this policy cannot be modeled. However, for a future ABM modeling data management (see Subsection 4.3.2), this policy would be implemented similar to the regulation.
- Regulation (sensors): This policy was demonstrated in the prototype through an increase of *sia* of the agents that have not yet adopted a sensor.
- Competence transfer: The transfer of competences concerning CSO tanks from municipalities to WWTP operators cannot be modeled in this prototype, as ownership or operation responsibilities were not included due to a lack of knowledge. This is discussed in Subsection 4.3.2.
- Subsidies (sensors): In other ABMs [Rai and Robinson, 2015], subsidies such as rebates impact the parameter *pb*. In Swiss urban drainage management, generally enough financial means are available and subsidies rather impact the attitude (*sia*) of the stakeholders.¹
- Education: Education aims at increasing the know-how of stakeholders. In the prototype increasing the parameter *know-how* affects the parameters *pb* and *sia* (see Subsection 2.3.2).

Except for the policy 'competence transfer' all the above policies impact the parameters related to TPB. Thus, more differentiated knowledge about the impact of policies should be acquired using a psychological approach. Further possibilities for policy evaluation also include the combination of policies, e.g. the policies 'regulation' and 'better technology' could easily be implemented simultaneously. However, further policies could not be evaluated due to time reasons.

4.2 Analysis of the Prototype

4.2.1 Numerical Experiments

The most significant numerical experiment is the one relating to opinion dynamics (Exp. 4), where the uncertainty of opinion was assigned randomly. For the municipalities, a significant variation of the outcome can be observed. This points out the uncertainty regarding the opinion dynamics. In the baseline and Exp. 5, either convergence or polarization is observed, respectively, depending on the initialization of the opinion uncertainty. These results also indicate that opinion dynamics are a sensitive point in the ABM prototype. Furthermore, it is known that the bounded confidence model is sensitive to noise [Helbing, 2012, p. 131-138] as well as to the network topology [Meadows and Cliff, 2013]. However, a different network configuration, communication schedule or the shift concerning order of agent interactions did not show notable differences in results. This indicates a certain 'robustness' of the prototype to these changes, even though it is not possible to exhaust all possible numerical experiments in the model, e.g. regarding network topology. In a further development of the prototype, a more detailed analysis of the sensitivity of the opinion dynamics towards network topology and randomness should be made.

¹According to a domain expert.

Even though the numerical experiment regarding a different communication schedule (Exp. 2) only showed a small difference to the baseline scenario, it is important to mention the following point. As a simplification for the prototype, it is assumed that the communication schedule is the same for all agents depending on their type. In reality, however, the communication frequency depends strongly on the interest and involvement of the responsible people.²

4.2.2 Sensitivity Analysis

The sensitivity analysis shows that the initial attitude of WWTP operators (*sia*) has the most important impact on the share of WWTP operators that adopted sensors by the end of the simulation period. Equally, the municipalities' initial attitude has the largest effect on the municipalities' sensor adoption. The influence of the engineers' and cantonal authorities' initial *sia* is rather small. This can be explained by the small number of agents that represent the authorities and engineers and the fact that the exchange among agents happens 'on eye level' in the relative agreement algorithm. In a further development of the prototype, different weights for interaction in the RA Algorithm (μ) could be included to account for the hierarchy among agents. However, the small influence of cantonal authorities and engineers could, transposed to the real world, indicate that wide-spread sensor adoption cannot be reached by the power of persuasion of individuals. Rather, a policy should aim at the municipalities and WWTP operators directly or at least increase the influence of these individuals (e.g. through a regulation). The second most important parameter *sia_threshold*, i.e. the attitude threshold above which an agent adopts a sensor. This finding highlights the importance of the behavior model to specify this parameter. In a further development of the prototype, a detailed sensitivity analysis should be performed.

4.3 Plausibility

4.3.1 Theory of Planned Behavior

When the Theory of Planned Behaviour is applied as a theoretical framework, there are certain steps that need to be followed to obtain plausible results, such as defining the behaviour clearly and performing elicitation interviews. Then, a questionnaire has to be developed for that specific purpose. Furthermore, the respondent's actual behaviour needs to be recorded, e.g. if the agent adopted a sensor in his CSO tank within a year after the survey. In our case, the survey was not conducted with the purpose of using TPB, but to obtain information about measurement technology in Swiss urban drainage. The consequences of using the survey data nonetheless can be observed in the agent initialization, where no clear attitude threshold can be drawn between agents with and without sensors. If the Methodology of TPB would be applied, one could expect more distinct distributions of agent's attitude and perceived behavioural control with more predictive power about agent behavior. If a study using TPB was to be conducted, the choice of variables in the ABM would have to be reconsidered. Furthermore, an elaborate preregistration of the ABM should be made to improve its quality [Eberlen et al., 2017]. However, following this procedure would exceed the time scope of this master thesis.

4.3.2 Expert Discussion

The choice of stakeholders

An individual agent used in the prototype may include several persons in reality, e.g. a cantonal authority with regional departments. However, the opinion dynamics and TPB refer to individuals. While observations on the scale of individuals instead of summarized agents would be more suitable for modeling opinion dynamics and agent behavior, the generation of agents and their social network on the basis of geo-spatial data is a valid alternative for a prototype and might be combined with more detailed data regarding stakeholders once it is available.

According to experts, stakeholders from the municipality, as well as wastewater associations, should be differentiated into political, administration and practical/technical domains. Furthermore, the hard- and software providers of monitoring technology should be included in the model. As there

²According to an expert of urban drainage management.

can be personalities that actively promote or inhibit sensor adoption in different positions of urban drainage management, these individuals should be differentiated and not summarized into a single agent.

Sensor adoption or data management?

The model output differentiates between sensor adoption by municipalities and sensor adoption by WWTP operators. The focus was laid on the decision of agents to adopt sensors rather than the actual installation of sensors in CSO tanks. It is assumed that both the municipalities and the WWTPs operators have the possibility to adopt sensors, independently of their ownership of CSO tanks. Due to the lack of knowledge about the ownership or operation of CSO tanks, as well as the number of CSO tanks present (see Appendix B.1), the introduction of specific CSO tanks would have introduced an additional uncertainty into the prototype. However, in a further development of the prototype, the following question should be asked:

Which share of the CSO tanks operated in a canton or subregion are equipped with a water level meter, the measurements of which are recorded appropriately (with high temporal resolution and permanently)?³

The subsequent question after the systematic evaluation of monitoring data would still go too far for the current situation. The methodology applied in this prototype, however, could be adapted to the question mentioned beforehand. Regarding TPB, the modeled behavior would be the appropriate recording of monitoring data and the variables should be chosen accordingly.

4.3.3 Validation

As mentioned in Section 2.1, the validation of ABMs frequently poses a challenge and has to be adapted on a case-to-case basis. This was also done in the case of this prototype, where elements from two different approaches were combined. The first element is the 'rule-catalog' from the methodology suggested by Tillman (2001). Originally, it is a list of if-then-rules that have to be agreed to by experts, a time-consuming approach which demands a series of round-table meetings among experts. Furthermore, it became apparent that the adoption of sensors depends to a large extent on the personalities of the responsible people for wastewater treatment and urban drainage management.^{??} Thus, TPB from the methodology suggested by Rai and Robinson (2015) was introduced to better account for psychological factors. The 'rule-catalog' proved very useful for communication and ensures that the ABM does not drift away from the reality of Swiss urban drainage management. The assumptions taken for the model, even though not in the form of if-then-rules, were listed and could all be at least partly agreed by the experts (see Appendix I). The methodology using TPB and the RA Algorithm [Rai and Robinson, 2015] relies on the validation through different empirical data sets. In the case of this prototype, comparable data sets are not available. Thus, the prototype cannot be validated. In the next subsection, data sets for an improved plausibility of the prototype in a further development are listed.

4.3.4 Empirical Data

To obtain plausible quantitative results with this prototype, more empirical data would be necessary. In the following, some suggestions for data sets from different categories are made, which would be useful for the further development of the prototype:

Psychology: A study including a survey could be performed using the methodology of TPB to investigate the behavior of stakeholders. In the ABM, this data set could be used for determining the attitude towards sensor adoption (or recording monitoring data appropriately) and the impact of policies on stakeholders. If such a study was to be performed, a preregistration of the ABM would improve its quality.

Social network: For further investigation of the opinion dynamics among stakeholders, detailed data about the connections between them would be beneficial. It

³Suggested by an expert.

might be combined with the geospatial data used for network configuration in this prototype by e.g. introducing subsystems where currently multiple stakeholders are modeled as a single agent. Such data is currently collected in the scope of the POLAAR project.

- Organization:** As not all stakeholders in of Swiss urban drainage management could participate in a psychological study, agent attributes like attitude could be modeled for a larger group of agents, e.g. through a multinomial logit model, rather than assigned randomly like in this prototype. Easier available data sets that show correlations with sensor adoption or good data management would be suitable for this purpose. The organization of urban drainage management (Figure 2.1) could have a stronger correlation to sensor adoption than e.g. technical data of WWTPs. In a first approach, the survey among municipalities [Ladner, 2017] (Appendix B) could be integrated into the geo-spatial data set of municipalities (Data Set C.1.6).
- CSO tanks:** Only for the canton of Bern, a registry of all CSO tanks (and other infrastructure) was readily available. To improve the knowledge about CSO tanks in Switzerland, such registries would be beneficial for all cantons. There, also the monitoring equipment could be included.
- Sensors:** Historical data about sensor adoption would be useful for adjusting model parameters. Such data is not available, but if data management was to be modeled in an ABM, it might be possible to obtain metadata of CSO monitoring, which would indicate the start of the monitoring process.

4.4 Are ABMs useful?

ABM for system understanding

Through the process of developing this prototype, knowledge from the domain of Swiss urban drainage management, psychology, and social simulation was combined in a model and implemented on a computer for the evaluation of policies. A new, multidisciplinary view of the problem concerning sensor adoption in CSO tanks was developed. Thus, developing an ABM is useful for system understanding.

ABM for policy evaluation

The prototype developed in this thesis could not be validated. In order to do so, several sets of empirical data would be needed, some of which would need a large effort to obtain, e.g. a survey according to TPB, or might not be obtainable at all such as historical data of sensor adoption. Thus, no predictive power can be attributed to the prototype.

4.5 Software implementation

The **Mesa** framework was suitable for the development of this prototype. A single run of the prototype for entire Switzerland could be completed in under one minute. If e.g. subsystems would be included into the prototype, a faster version could be implemented to benefit from **Mesa**'s multiprocessing tools. Other ABM and simulation tools exist, that are more apt for medium to large-scale scenarios. Some ABMs even make use of GPU [Saprykin et al., 2019], decreasing the computation time considerably. Furthermore, a surrogate model could be trained to speed up calibration and sensitivity analysis [Zhang et al., 2020]. However, these approaches would involve a high effort.

5 Conclusion

A prototype of an ABM was developed, with the aim to evaluate policies regarding sensor adoption in CSO tanks. Data was collected, analyzed and integrated into the prototype, along with prior knowledge about stakeholders and their interactions. Psychological models for behavior and opinion dynamics were considered and how they can be implemented in an agent-based computer environment. Afterwards, scenarios for policy analysis were simulated discussed and the prototype's uncertainties were evaluated. The uncertainties prevailed and no predictive power can be attributed to the prototype. Through the process of developing the prototype, a new multi-disciplinary view of sensor adoption in CSO tanks was developed. The questions stated in the introduction can be answered as follows:

How can stakeholder behavior and interactions be modeled?

The stakeholder behavior is modeled based on an adaption of the established Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) from the domain of psychology. It is assumed that agents adopt sensors based on their attitude towards sensor adoption. During each time step of the simulation period, agents communicate with their neighbors on the social network and change their attitude towards sensor adoption under the influence of other agents. This process is governed by the Relative Agreement algorithm, an opinion dynamics model that assumes bounded confidence, i.e. an agent is only influenced by other agents with similar attitudes towards sensor adoption.

How can available prior knowledge and data be integrated into an ABM prototype for CSO sensor adoption in Switzerland?

The model depends on the knowledge of domain experts to determine the important stakeholders of Swiss urban drainage management that are then modeled as agents and their tasks. Furthermore, the communication between different stakeholder groups is derived from expert knowledge. Assumptions for the model are listed in a rule-catalog to be validated by experts. The model agents, such as the WWTP operators, the cantonal authorities, and municipalities are based on geo-spatial data sets including the administrative borders of Switzerland and location and catchment areas of WWTPs. To simulate local interaction, a social network between the agents was generated from these geo-spatial data sets as well. The initial attitudes towards sensor adoption of WWTP operator and cantonal authority agents are estimated using survey data. Various other data sets were collected and analyzed during the course of this thesis.

What are effective policies that increase sensor adoption?

A regulation is the most effective policy that was modeled, followed by the introduction of better technology. Results suggest that the influence of cantonal authorities and engineers has a small impact on sensor adoption compared to the influence of WWTP operators and municipalities. Numbers are explicitly not mentioned here not to convey a wrong impression of exactitude of the model results.

What are the largest uncertainties inherent in the ABM prototype?

The sensitivity analysis of the prototype highlights the importance of the agent's initial attitudes. For the cantonal authority and WWTP operators, these are calculated based on survey data using TPB. However, the available survey was not performed after the methodology of TPB, which strongly limits the reliability of the attitude estimates. Furthermore, a numerical experiment performed to analyze the robustness of prototype points towards uncertainties in the opinion dynamics. A temporal validation of the model with empirical data cannot be performed, due to the unavailability of e.g. a time series of sensor adoption.

What is necessary for the development of a plausible ABM in the context of sensor adoption in CSO tanks?

To validate an ABM poses a challenge on a case-to-case basis. In the case of the developed prototype, various empirical data sets would be necessary. Firstly, for the initialization of the agent's attitudes towards sensor adoption, data from a survey conducted according to the methodology of

TPB would be needed, along with more fine-grained data about the organization of urban drainage management and CSO tanks in Switzerland. Furthermore, historical data about sensor adoption is essential for the adjustment of parameters and the temporal validation of the model output. The sensitivity of the opinion dynamics towards different network topology should also be analyzed more thoroughly than it was possible in the scope of this master thesis. Gathering all this empirical data consists in a considerable effort. If this effort is made, an elaborate preregistration of the ABM is worthwhile.

Is the approach of ABM useful in the context of sensor adoption in CSO tanks?

The method of ABM has drawbacks concerning validation and the prediction of the impact of policies has to be evaluated carefully. However, its benefits regarding system understanding should not be underestimated. During the development of this prototype, empirical data, knowledge from experts in the domain of urban drainage management, and theoretical concepts for modeling behavior and opinion dynamics were integrated into a single model. This led to a new understanding of the deficits regarding sensor adoption in CSO tanks.

Outlook

Three concrete possibilities for further research are suggested:

1. Establishing a geo-spatial data base containing information about the organization of Swiss urban drainage, ownership and operation of infrastructure elements. Such a geo-spatial data base provides a Swiss wide overview on how the infrastructure is currently managed. This could help to understand competencies and distribution of roles and tasks, also in terms of sensor adoption and handling of monitoring data.
2. Adapting the ABM prototype to analyze social networks of stakeholders of urban drainage management. Within the project POLAAR, a survey is currently conducted to gather data about socio-technical networks of urban wastewater infrastructure management. Obtained survey data may improve the understanding of interactions between stakeholders and therefore refine the opinion dynamics within the ABM prototype.
3. An identification of barriers to monitoring CSOs of psychological nature through TPB could contribute to a better representation of the modeled agent behaviour. As a consequence, an ABM could be developed with a complete and less simplified implementation of TPB.

Bibliography

- [AVA, 2020] AVA (2020). Abwasserverband altenrhein geschäftsbericht 2019.
- [Ajzen, 1991] Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2):179–211.
- [Ajzen, 2013] Ajzen, I. (2013). Theory of planned behaviour questionnaire. measurement instrument database for the social science. Retrieved from www.midss.ie.
- [Baudirektion Kanton Zürich, 2015] Baudirektion Kanton Zürich, A. A. (2015). Genereller entwässerungsplan (gep) gep-check.
- [Baumann, 2017] Baumann, P. (2017). *Regenbecken im Mischsystem Messen, Bewerten und Optimieren : Praxisleitfaden für den Betrieb von Regenbecken*. DWA-Landesverband Baden-Württemberg, Stuttgart.
- [Berglund, 2015] Berglund, E. Z. (2015). Using agent-based modeling for water resources planning and management. *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 141(11):04015025.
- [Campolongo et al., 2007] Campolongo, F., Cariboni, J., and Saltelli, A. (2007). An effective screening design for sensitivity analysis of large models. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 22(10):1509–1518.
- [Caprioli et al., 2020] Caprioli, C., Bottero, M., and Angelis, E. D. (2020). Supporting policy design for the diffusion of cleaner technologies: A spatial empirical agent-based model. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(10):581.
- [Clifforde et al., 2006] Clifforde, I. T., Crabtree, R. W., and Andrews, H. O. (2006). 10 years experience of cso management in the united kingdom. WEFTEC 06.
- [Conte and Paolucci, 2014] Conte, R. and Paolucci, M. (2014). On agent-based modeling and computational social science. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5.
- [Deffuant et al., 2002] Deffuant, G., Amblard, F., Weisbuch, G., and Faure, T. (2002). How can extremism prevail? a study based on the relative agreement interaction model. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation (JASSS)*, 5(4).
- [Dittmer, 2015] Dittmer, U., e. a. (2015). Kenngrößen für die bewertung des betriebs von regenüberlaufbecken. *Jahrestagung der Lehrer und Obleute der Kläranlagen- und Kanal-Nachbarschaften des DWA-Landesverbands Baden-Württemberg*.
- [Eawag, 2015] Eawag (2015). Medienmitteilung - 100 kläranlagen müssen aufrüsten â eawag infotag 2015. <https://www.admin.ch/gov/de/start/dokumentation/medienmitteilungen.msg-id-58567.html>. accessed on 25.02.2021.
- [Eberlen et al., 2017] Eberlen, J., Scholz, G., and Gagliolo, M. (2017). Simulate this! an introduction to agent-based models and their power to improve your research practice. *International Review of Social Psychology*, 30(1):149.
- [Gardner, 1970] Gardner, M. (1970). The fantastic combinations of john conway’s new solitaire game ”life” by martin gardner. *Scientific American - Mathematical Games*, 223:120–123.
- [Grimm and Berger, 2016] Grimm, V. and Berger, U. (2016). Robustness analysis: Deconstructing computational models for ecological theory and applications. *Ecological Modelling*, 326:162–167.
- [Grimm et al., 2010] Grimm, V., Berger, U., DeAngelis, D. L., Polhill, J. G., Giske, J., and Railsback, S. F. (2010). The ODD protocol: A review and first update. *Ecological Modelling*, 221(23):2760–2768.

- [Hegselmann and Krause, 2002] Hegselmann, R. and Krause, U. (2002). Opinion dynamics and bounded confidence models, analysis, and simulation. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation (JASSS)*, 5(3).
- [Helbing, 2012] Helbing, D. (2012). *Social Self-Organization*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [Herman and Usher, 2017] Herman, J. and Usher, W. (2017). SALib: An open-source python library for sensitivity analysis. *The Journal of Open Source Software*, 2(9):97.
- [Hoffmann, 2014] Hoffmann, S. (2014). *Nachhaltige Wasserversorgung und Abwasserentsorgung in der Schweiz : Herausforderungen und Handlungsoptionen*. NFP 61, Bern.
- [Hoppe et al., 2019] Hoppe, H., Dittmer, U., Gruber, G., and Rieckermann, J. (2019). Datenbasierte planungs-, betriebs und vollzugskonzepte zur nachhaltigen regenwasserbehandlung.
- [Hoppe et al., 2016] Hoppe, H., Fricke, K., Kutsch, S., Massing, C., and Gruber, G. (2016). Messungen in entwässerungssystemen: Von "daten" zu "werten". *Aqua Urbanica*.
- [Kasargodu Anebagilu et al., 2021] Kasargodu Anebagilu, P., Dietrich, J., Prado-Stuardo, L., Morales, B., Winter, E., and Arumi, J. L. (2021). Application of the theory of planned behavior with agent-based modeling for sustainable management of vegetative filter strips. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 284:112014.
- [Kerkez et al., 2016] Kerkez, B., Gruden, C., Lewis, M., Montestruque, L., Quigley, M., Wong, B., Bedig, A., Kertesz, R., Braun, T., Cadwalader, O., Poresky, A., and Pak, C. (2016). Smarter stormwater systems. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 50(14):7267–7273.
- [Ladner, 2017] Ladner, A. (2017). Nationale gemeindeschreiberbefragung 2017. <http://www.andreasladner.ch/uebersicht.htm>, last accessed on 18.02.2021. Fragebogen: Gemeinden 2016, Daten: Daten 2016.
- [Ladner, 2020] Ladner, P. (2020). Praktikumsbericht, projekt polaar. Eawag. 23.9.2019 - 24.1.2020.
- [Maio et al., 1996] Maio, G. R., Bell, D. W., and Esses, V. M. (1996). Ambivalence and persuasion: The processing of messages about immigrant groups. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 32(6):513–536.
- [Manny, 2017] Manny, L. (2017). Policy-analyse im bereich gewässerschutz bei regenwetter. Master's thesis, RWTH Aachen Eawag.
- [Manny et al., 2018] Manny, L., Fischer, M., and Rieckermann, J. (2018). Policy-analyse für einen besseren gewässerschutz bei regenwetter. *Schriftenreihe Wasser Infrastruktur Ressourcen*, 1:139–151.
- [Manny et al., 2019] Manny, L., Fischer, M., Stauffer, P., and Rieckermann, J. (2019). Saubere gewässer dank messdatenmanagement - instrumente für einen guten umgang mit messdaten in der schweizer siedlungsentwässerung. *AQUA Gas*, (1).
- [Manzo, 2014] Manzo, G. (2014). *La simulation multi-agents : principes et applications aux phénomènes sociaux*. Presses de Sciences Po, Paris.
- [Marini et al., 2020] Marini, M., Chokani, N., and Abhari, R. S. (2020). COVID-19 epidemic in switzerland: Growth prediction and containment strategy using artificial intelligence and big data.
- [Maurer, 2012] Maurer, M. (2012). *Abwasserentsorgung 2025 in der Schweiz*. EAWAG, Dübendorf.
- [Meadows and Cliff, 2012] Meadows, M. and Cliff, D. (2012). Reexamining the relative agreement model of opinion dynamics. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 15(4).
- [Meadows and Cliff, 2013] Meadows, M. and Cliff, D. (2013). The relative agreement model of opinion dynamics in populations with complex social network structure. In *Complex Networks IV*, pages 71–79. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

- [Montserrat et al., 2016] Montserrat, A., Hofer, T., Poch, M., Muschalla, D., and Corominas, L. (2016). Using the duration of combined sewer overflow events for the calibration of sewer hydrodynamic models. *Urban Water Journal*, 14(8):782–788.
- [Mordvintsev et al., 2020] Mordvintsev, A., Randazzo, E., Niklasson, E., and Levin, M. (2020). Growing neural cellular automata. *Distill*. <https://distill.pub/2020/growing-ca>.
- [Morris, 1991] Morris, M. D. (1991). Factorial sampling plans for preliminary computational experiments. *Technometrics*, 33(2):161–174.
- [Mutzner et al., 2016] Mutzner, L., Staufer, P., and Ort, C. (2016). Model-based screening for critical wet-weather discharges related to micropollutants from urban areas. *Water Research*, 104:547–557.
- [Otto et al., 2020] Otto, I. M., Donges, J. F., Cremades, R., Bhowmik, A., Hewitt, R. J., Lucht, W., Rockström, J., Allerberger, F., McCaffrey, M., Doe, S. S. P., Lenferna, A., Morán, N., van Vuuren, D. P., and Schellnhuber, H. J. (2020). Social tipping dynamics for stabilizing earth’s climate by 2050. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(5):2354–2365.
- [Pistocchi and Dorati, 2018] Pistocchi, A. and Dorati, C. (2018). Combined sewer overflow management: Proof-of-concept of a screening level model for regional scale appraisal of measures. In *New Trends in Urban Drainage Modelling*, pages 937–941. Springer International Publishing.
- [Rai and Robinson, 2015] Rai, V. and Robinson, S. A. (2015). Agent-based modeling of energy technology adoption: Empirical integration of social, behavioral, economic, and environmental factors. *Environmental Modelling Software*, 70:163–177.
- [Rieckermann et al., 2017] Rieckermann, J., Gruber, G., and Hoppe, H. (2017). Zukunftsfähige systeme zur regenwasserbehandlung brauchendatenbasierte betriebs-, planungs- und vollzugskonzepte. *Institut für Siedlungswasserwirtschaft und Landschaftswasserbau, Schriftenreihe zur Wasserwirtschaft, TU Graz*, 75:C1–C30.
- [Saltelli, 2000] Saltelli, Chan, S. (2000). *Sensitivity Analysis*. John Wiley Sons.
- [Saprykin et al., 2019] Saprykin, A., Chokani, N., and Abhari, R. S. (2019). GEMSim: A GPU-accelerated multi-modal mobility simulator for large-scale scenarios. *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, 94:199–214.
- [Schelling, 1971] Schelling, T. C. (1971). Dynamic models of segregation. *Journal of Mathematical Sociology*, 1:143–186.
- [Singh, 2016] Singh, A. (2016). *GIS-based European Energy Systems Modelling to Assess Impact of Policy on Performance and Markets*. PhD thesis.
- [ten Broeke et al., 2016] ten Broeke, G., van Voorn, G., and Ligtenberg, A. (2016). Which sensitivity analysis method should i use for my agent-based model? *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 19(1).
- [Tillman, 2001] Tillman, D. E. (2001). *Stakeholder analysis in water supply systems*. PhD thesis.
- [VSA, 2009] VSA (2009). Verband schweizer abwasser- und gewässerschutzfachleute: Erläuterungen zum musterpflichtenheft für den generellen entwässerungsplan (gep).
- [Zhang et al., 2020] Zhang, Y., Li, Z., and Zhang, Y. (2020). Validation and calibration of an agent-based model: A surrogate approach. *Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society*, 2020:1–9.

A Implementation in Python

The entire Python code developed and used in this Master's thesis can be found on the following gitlab repository:

https://gitlab.switch.ch/manny/abm_prototype_2020

In the README, a link to the full documentation is included. The input data is stored on an external storage medium, as some data sets include sensitive information.

B Organization of Urban Drainage

In this chapter, additional analysis of data regarding the organization of urban drainage management and CSO tanks is included, which was conducted throughout this master thesis.

Figure B.1 shows an illustration of the deficits of CSO monitoring in Switzerland.

Figure B.1: Illustration of the Motivation for this Master Thesis. On the top left, an average CSO operator without sensor is shown. on the top right, an exemplary CSO operator is shown. The two figures on the bottom represent the current (left) and ideal (right) situation in Switzerland. The goal of this master thesis is to analyze policies that increase sensor adoption.

In Figure B.2, the evaluation of the survey among municipalities [Ladner, 2017] is included. The evaluated survey questions were the following:

- Are the performance limits in your municipality reached concerning wastewater/urban drainage management?
- In what form is wastewater/urban drainage organized in your municipality?

The questions did not differentiate between wastewater treatment and urban drainage management. Thus, no further distinctions could be made. An integration of this data set (Data Set C.1.5) into the geo-spatial data set of municipalities (Data Set C.1.6) would easily be possible and could even be combined with the WWTP catchment areas (Data Set C.1.4).

Figure B.3 shows a real network among stakeholders that are distinguished into the 4 different agent types used for the prototype.

Performance Limit (PL) / Inter-municipal Cooperation (IMC)

No PL visible	565	120	293	26	39	5
PL in sight	226	48	106	15	31	3
PL reached	80	13	34	5	10	0
PL crossed	15	4	14	1	3	0
Municipality not concerned	6	12	38	3	1	24
	Self-made	IMC contract	IMC judicial persons under public law	IMC judicial persons under private law	Collaboration with private provider	Not a task / concern of the municipality

Figure B.2: Results concerning wastewater/urban drainage of the survey 'Nationale Gemeindegemeinschaftsbefragung 2017' [Ladner, 2017]. 903 of the municipality officials claimed that the municipality organizes wastewater/urban drainage on its own, while 823 of them are organized in some form of collaboration with other municipalities or private providers.

B.1 Evaluation of Data Sets concerning CSO Tanks

During the Master's thesis, three data sets concerning CSO tanks operated by wastewater associations were available:

Data Set C.1.1 The amount of CSO tanks operated by the respondents of the wastewater association survey.

Data Set C.1.7 The inventory of CSO tanks (and other infrastructure elements) from the canton of Bern.

Data Set C.1.3 The inventory of external infrastructure elements provided by Chestonag Automation AG.

To combine these data sets, the number of CSOs per WWTP was calculated or extracted separately in each data set and then matched to the WWTPs from the geospatial (Data Set C.1.4) using the WWTP ID. This allows the combination of technical properties of WWTPs. In Figure B.4, the number of WWTP operators operating a certain number of CSO tanks is illustrated. It can be found that most WWTPs are only connected to a small number of CSO tanks (1-10). How many CSO tanks are connected to a WWTP does not seem to be correlated with its size, as illustrated in Figure B.5.

It is important to mention here, that these three Data Sets contradict each other in a lot of cases and it is not sure, how many CSO tanks can be attributed to the average WWTP. Thus, the decision was taken to refrain from introducing an exact number of CSO tanks into the prototype, as the focus of the prototype lies on the decision to adopt a sensor rather than the exact number of CSO tanks equipped with sensors. Including an exact number of CSO tanks would introduce an additional uncertainty. Figure B.5 was created with the aim to identify a correlation between technical aspects of a WWTP and the number of CSO tanks connected. This would allow for modelling the number of CSO tanks attributed to each WWTP. However, considering the limited time available and the contradictions within the data sets, we refrained from modeling the number of CSO tanks associated to a WWTP.

Figure B.4: The amount of WWTP operators that operate a certain number of CSO tanks. The Data Sets C.1.7, C.1.1, and C.1.3 were combined. The latter data set also includes other special constructions ('Aussenwerke').

Figure B.5: The amount of CSO tanks by different WWTPs vs the size of the WWTPs. The Data Sets C.1.7, C.1.1, and C.1.3 were combined. The latter data set also includes other special constructions ('Aussenwerke').

B.2 Policies

The Table in Figure B.6, shows the results regarding the most effective policies of the survey among wastewater associations and cantonal authorities [Manny, 2017].

Tabelle 3: Instrumente-Ranking der Abwasserverbände (AV) und Kantone (K) sowie spezifischer Adressat für die jeweiligen Instrumente (s. Anhang C.4). Die Einführung von Zielvorgaben steht sowohl für Abwasserverbände als auch kantonale Fachstellen an erster Stelle.

Mögliches Instrument	Kategorie	Rank (AV)	Rank (K)	Wer (AV)	Wer (K)
Vorschrift (Messtechnik)	Gesetz/VO	2	4	B/ K	B
Zielvorgaben (Messdaten)	Gesetz/VO	1	1	B/ K	B
Performance-Indikatoren	Techn. Richtlinie	5	9	VSA	B
Subvention (Messtechnik)	Finanz. Anreiz	3	6	B	K
Subvention (Messdaten)	Finanz. Anreiz	5	7	B	K
Bessere Produkte	Industrie	9	9		
Angepasste Dienstleistungen	Industrie	7	5		
Aus- und Weiterbildung	Bildung	8	3		
Veranstaltungen	Bildung	7	6	VSA	
Verstärkte Aufsichtsfunktion	Organisation	6	8		
Kompetenz-Verlagerung	Organisation	4	2		
Eigener Vorschlag		10			

AV: Abwasserverbände, K: Kantone, B: Bund, VO: Verordnung

Figure B.6: Table containing the ranking of policies resulting from the survey conducted among wastewater associations and cantonal authorities [Manny, 2017].

C Data

C.1 Overview

The following list presents the data sets which were used during the course of this Master's thesis:

- Survey wastewater associations
- Interviews & survey cantonal authorities
- Chestonag Aussenbauwerke
- WWTPs and catchment areas geodata
- Municipality survey
- Geodata Switzerland
- CSO tank survey canton Bern

Please find a description of each data set below.

C.1.1 Survey wastewater associations

Name: Umfrage Gewässerschutz bei Regenwetter - Organisation der Siedlungsentwässerung

Source: Survey conducted during the Master's thesis [Manny, 2017].

Year: 2017

Description: The survey evaluates the status of measurement technology and data management in the domain of urban drainage among Swiss wastewater associations, focusing on CSO tanks. The online survey was sent to the 162 known wastewater associations, 118 of which replied.

Used for: In this thesis, the survey data was used for calculating the initial state of the WWTP operator agent (Subsection 2.3.5). Furthermore, the data set was combined with the geodata of WWTPs, the CSO tank survey of canton Bern, and the novel Chestonag special construction data set to analyze the number of CSOs connected to different WWTPs.

C.1.2 Interviews & survey cantonal authorities

Name: Organisation der Siedlungsentwässerung für den Gewässerschutz bei Regenwetter - Befragung der Schweizer Kantone

Source: Survey conducted by Liliane Manny in the scope of the POLAAR project [Manny et al., 2018].

Year: 2017

Description: All 26 cantonal authorities replied to a online survey concerning the handling of measurement data in urban drainage in the respective canton. Furthermore, 22 cantonal authorities were assigned scores from 1 to 10 for problem recognition, the perceived use of measurement technology, the encouragement towards municipalities, and the extent to which measurement data is used for compliance assessment.

Used for: Data from the survey is used for the initialization of the WWTP operator agent (Subsection 2.3.5). The opinion of the cantonal authority agent is initialized by averaging the rating over the 4 evaluated domains mentioned above.

C.1.3 Chestonag Aussenbauwerke

Name: Anlagen mit Aussenbauwerken

Source: Chestonag Automation AG

Year: 2020

Description: List of 144 WWTPs with the associated number of external infrastructure elements.

Used for: Combination with Data Sets C.1.7, C.1.1 C.1.4 for the analysis of the number of CSO tanks connected to WWTPs (Section B.1).

C.1.4 WWTPs and catchment areas geodata

Name: Einzugsgebiete der Kläranlagen der Schweiz, überarbeitet 2014; Kläranlagen der Schweiz ©2014, Eawag: überarbeitet auf der Basis des Projektes: Maurer M. und Herlyn A. (2007) Zustand, Kosten und Investitionsbedarf der schweizerischen Abwasserentsorgung. Eawag/Bafu Bericht.
Weitere Information:
http://www.eawag.ch/forschung/sww/schwerpunkte/infrastrukturen/zustand_kosten/SEI21_Abschlussbericht.pdf

Source: Eawag

Year: 2014

Description: Geographical locations, catchment areas and technical properties of WWTPs in Switzerland.

Used for: Generating Agents (Subsection 2.3.1) and their social network (Subsection 2.3.6, evaluation of CSO data (Section B.1).

C.1.5 Municipality survey

Name: Nationale Gemeindeschreiberbefragung 2017

Source: [Ladner, 2017], <http://www.andreasladner.ch/uebersicht.htm>, last accessed on 18.02.2021

Year: 2017

Description: Survey among the municipalities of Switzerland.

Used for: Evaluation of two questions regarding wastewater treatment / urban drainage.

C.1.6 Geodata Switzerland

Name: swissBOUNDARIES3D

Source: Bundesamt für Landestopografie: <https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/de/geodata/landscape/boundaries3d.html>

Year: 2020

Description: Includes the administrative boundaries of Switzerland and the Principality of Liechtenstein, i.e. boundaries of cantons and municipalities.

Used for: Generating agents (cantonal authorities and municipalities) as described in Subsection 2.3.1.

C.1.7 CSO tank survey canton Bern

- Name:** Umfrage Sonderbauwerke Kanalisation, Auswertungsbericht Regenbecken Datenbank Sonderbauwerke
- Source:** AWA-BE (Amt für Wasser und Abfall des Kantons Bern, Fachbereich Trinkwasser und Abwasser)
- Year:** 2018
- Description:** Database of CSO tanks on the cantonal territory of Bern. Included are category, ownership relations, equipment, and technical properties of the CSO tanks.
- Used for:** Combination with Data Sets C.1.7, C.1.1 C.1.4 for the analysis of the number of CSO tanks connected to WWTPs (Section B.1).

D Agent Parameters from Survey Data

In this section, complementary information to Subsection 2.3.5 is given.

How *sia* parameters are estimated from the survey

A value for the know-how of each agent is found by combining survey responses to questions concerning the sensor technology already implemented in the CSO tanks as well as sensors in sewers and rain meters. Experience related to sensors in CSO tanks is weighted twice as much as experience related to other domains. From the survey, the questions 14, 15, and 16 ask for the number of rain meters and sensors that are adopted in CSO tanks or sewers. To mitigate the influence of high numbers, the logarithm of these values is used. Questions 17 and 18 treat the quantities that are measured in CSO tanks and sewers, which can take either the value 0 or 1. Where the questionnaire was not complete, the value 0 was used. The parameter *vision* reflects the individual attitude of the respondent towards real-time control of the sewers and the operation of infrastructure besides the WWTP (integral urban water management). Finally, the social influence consists of the encouragement / motivation that the cantonal authority exerts on the wastewater association (assessment by Manny), multiplied by the quality of cooperation claimed by the wastewater association. Furthermore, the participation in professional events increases the social influence.

How the parameters are normalized

The mean of the parameters *know-how*, *vision* and *social influence* is taken and normalized such that the lowest value of *sia* lies at 0.05 and the highest value at 0.95. In a later step, the range of *sia* will be extended by varying the values randomly within a range of 0.1. The outcome of the parameter calculations is shown in Figure D.2.

The calculation of *pbc* from the survey

In Table 2.2, the factors taken into account for the calculation of *pbc* are listed. It is assumed that the freedom of decision and the financial freedom of the wastewater association towards the associated municipalities plays a role. Furthermore, a higher amount of operated CSO tanks increases the perceived behavioural control of the WWTP operator, as well as the ownership or a pending renovation of CSO tanks. An agent's know-how concerning sensor adoption is also assumed to have a positive influence on his feeling of control, therefore the parameter *know-how* (Table 2.1) is taken into account. The most important factor, however, is whether an agent operates CSO tanks or not. If not, *pbc* is set to zero. As the survey responses to questions 8 and 9 were sometimes ambiguous, both questions are taken into account. The survey questions can be found below.

Survey Questions

In the following the relevant survey questions relating to Table 2.2 and 2.1 can be found.

- 5 Wie beurteilen Sie die Freiheiten Ihres Abwasserverbands gegenüber den Verbandsgemeinden?
 - 5.1 Bei Entscheidungen (für den operativen Betrieb und Unterhalt)
 - 5.2 Für Finanzkompetenzen (Investitionen im Rahmen der Planung)
- 8 Welche Anlagen betreibt Ihr Abwasserverband zusätzlich zur ARA?
 - 8.1 Regenbecken (RB), die sich im Eigentum der Gemeinden befinden

Figure D.1: The unnormalized results from the calculation according to Table 2.1 and 2.2.

Figure D.2: The parameters *sia* and *pbc* of the survey respondents by WWTP size.

8.2 Regenbecken (RB) im eigenen Besitz

- 9** Wie viele Regenbecken (RB) betreibt Ihr Abwasserverband?
- 11** Stehen in den nächsten 5 Jahren Investitionen für die Sanierung eines Regenbeckens (RB) an?
- 14** Wie viele Ihrer Regenbecken sind mit mindestens einem solcher Messgeräte ausgestattet? (Überlaufdetektoren, Sonden zur Messung des Wasserstands oder der Wasserqualität, usw.)
- 15** Wie viele solcher Messgeräte sind insgesamt im Kanalnetz installiert? (Drucksonden zur Messung des Wasserstands, Durchfluss-Messgeräte, z.B. Radar, MID, Ultraschall, usw.)
- 16** Wie viele stationäre Regenmesser betreibt Ihr Abwasserverband?
- 17** Unten sehen Sie eine Auswahl an Messgrößen, die an Regenbecken (RB) erfasst werden können. Bitte kreuzen Sie jene Messgrößen an, welche Ihr Abwasserverband aufzeichnet.
- 17.1** Weiterleitmenge zur ARA [l/s]
- 17.2** Wasserstand im Regenbecken [m]
- 17.3** Entlastungsdauer
- 17.4** Entlastungshäufigkeit
- 17.5** Entlastungsmenge
- 18** Unten sehen Sie eine Auswahl an Messgrößen, die kontinuierlich im Kanalnetz erfasst werden können. Bitte kreuzen Sie jene Messgrößen an, welche Ihr Abwasserverband aufzeichnet.
- 18.1** Wasserstand [m]
- 18.2** Durchfluss [m²/s]
- 18.3** Wasserqualitäts-Parameter (z.B. Temperatur, elektrische Leitfähigkeit, pH, Ammonium, Nitrat, CSB)
- 33** Wie beurteilen Sie die Zusammenarbeit mit der kantonalen Fachstelle für den Bereich Siedlungsentwässerung?
- 34** Haben Mitarbeitende Ihres Abwasserverbands innerhalb des vergangenen Jahres an einer der folgenden fachlichen Veranstaltungen teilgenommen?
- IFAT
 - Treffen der VSA-Kompetenzzentren Siedlungsentwässerung, Gewässer, Abwasser oder Kanalisation
 - Aqua Urbanica Konferenz
 - Veranstaltung der kantonalen Fachstelle im Bereich Siedlungsentwässerung
 - Kundenveranstaltung von Ingenieur- und Planungsbüros
 - Kundenveranstaltung von einem Unternehmen mit Bezug zu Messtechnik oder Automation
- 35** Eine mögliche Zukunftsvision: Regenabwasseranlagen und Kanalnetze sind mit einer Vielzahl an Messgeräten ausgestattet. Die Messsignale werden über ein flächendeckendes Drahtlosnetzwerk live auf ein Leitsystem übertragen, automatisch überprüft, ausgewertet und archiviert. Diese permanente Überwachung der Anlagen wird durch die fortschreitende technologische Entwicklung in den Bereichen Kommunikation, Steuerungs- und Regelungstechnik und Automation ermöglicht. Was halten Sie persönlich von der beschriebenen Vision?
- 35.1** Ich befürworte diese Vision und bin generell offen für die Verwendung solcher moderner Technologien für die Anlagen unseres Abwasserverbands.
- 35.2** Ich lehne diese Vision ab, da ich eher wenig von der Verwendung solcher moderner Technologien für die Anlagen unseres Abwasserverbands halte.
- 35.3** Ich befürworte diese Vision unter folgender Voraussetzung: ...

- 36** Halten Sie es für sinnvoll, dass der Abwasserverband langfristig sowohl die ARA als auch alle Anlagen der Siedlungsentwässerung betreibt?
- 36.1** Ja, sinnvoll ist die übernahme aller Regenabwasseranlagen.
- 36.2** Ja, sinnvoll ist die übernahme aller Regenabwasseranlagen und der regional bedeutenden Kanalisation.
- 36.3** Ja, sinnvoll ist die übernahme aller Regenabwasseranlagen und der gesamten Kanalisation im Verbandsgebiet

E Relative Agreement Algorithm

The Relative Agreement algorithm [Deffuant et al., 2002, Hegselmann and Krause, 2002, Meadows and Cliff, 2012] is a way to model opinion dynamics in an ABM. Each agent has an opinion sia and a uncertainty of that opinion u . When two agents interact, while agent i influences agent j . The algorithm proceeds as follows:

The opinions sia of two agents are considered. In Equation E.1, the overlap of the uncertainties h_{ij} is calculated, while the uncertainties span from $sia - u$ to $sia + u$ for each agent.

$$h_{ij} = \min((sia_i + u_i), (sia_j + u_j)) - \max((sia_i - u_i), (sia_j - u_j)) \quad (\text{E.1})$$

The non-overlap is subtracted from the overlap to find the absolute agreement in Equation E.2.

$$h_{ij} - (2u_i - h_{ij}) = 2(h_{ij} - u_i) \quad (\text{E.2})$$

Then, the relative agreement is calculated in Equation E.3. Each agent has 'bounded confidence' into the opinions of its interaction partner, and agent j will only change its sia if the expression in Equation E.3 is greater than zero.

$$\frac{2(h_{ij} - u_i)}{2u_i} = \frac{h_{ij}}{u_i} - 1 \quad (\text{E.3})$$

Finally, the sia and u of agent i are updated as described in Equations E.4 and E.5. The change of sia is proportional to a factor μ , the relative agreement and the difference of opinions.

$$sia_j = sia_j + \mu \left(\left(\frac{h_{ij}}{u_i} \right) - 1 \right) (sia_i - sia_j) \quad (\text{E.4})$$

$$u_j = u_j + \mu \left(\left(\frac{h_{ij}}{u_i} \right) - 1 \right) (u_i - u_j) \quad (\text{E.5})$$

Good descriptions of the RA algorithm can also be found in other ABMs that use this approach [Caprioli et al., 2020], Appendix [Rai and Robinson, 2015].

Scheduling of interactions

In the model, the interactions are implemented on the social network, transformed into a bidirectional graph. Each agent sends its sia and u to the neighbors according to the communication schedule. The communication schedule determines the other agent types (WWTP operator, municipality etc.) that the agent of a certain type communicates to in the current time step. The agent j receives sia and u from all agents that have sent the values, i.e. attributed to the link of the social network pointing towards agent j . Agent j adds up the changes that these values will cause to its sia and u and then updates its states.

F Scenarios and Numerical Experiments

All numerical experiments and scenarios are simulated for the whole of Switzerland within a time span of 10 years, starting in 2017 and ending in 2027. This corresponds to 120 time steps of 1 month. Scenario 0 is the baseline for later comparisons. The numerical experiments aim at the analysis of uncertainties within the model and the parameters while Scenarios 1-3 demonstrate how policies can be implemented within the model. Figure F.1 shows an overview of the results of the numerical experiments and scenarios for the WWTP operators.

Figure F.1: Overview of all scenarios and numerical experiments. The share of WWTP operators after a 10 years simulation period, 100 iterations each scenario / numerical experiment. Sc. 2 and 3 show the highest share of agents with sensors. Compared to Figure 3.1, a smaller variation of the results is observed for the WWTP operators. The reason for this is the initialization of the agents' *sia*, *pb*, and *u*, that are sampled randomly each iteration for the municipalities, but not for the WWTP operators.

F.1 Scenario 1 - Baseline Scenario (GEP)

Description: This scenario uses the best knowledge available at the moment and is based on data evaluations, complemented by expert knowledge¹ where no data

¹Questionnaire filled in by Reto Battaglia on 18.02.2021

is available. In this scenario, the GEP ² is taking place.

- Purpose:** Adjustment of model parameters and establishment of a baseline for comparison of other scenarios and policies (Subsection 3.1.1).
- Social network:** Created according to Subsection 2.3.6.
- Agent initialization:** WWTP operator and cantonal authority *sia*, *pb*c, and *u* is initialized according to Subsection 2.3.5 and D. For the engineers and the municipalities, *sia* and *pb*c are generated from a gamma distribution similar to the expert's response to the questionnaire (municipalities: scale 0.05, shape 8; engineers: scale 0.05, shape 3, where the value drawn from the distribution is subtracted from 1, see Figure G.1). As *sia* and *pb*c correlate due to the similar calculation (Figure 2.6), both are sampled from the same distribution. *u* is generated accordingly using the inverse of the absolute value of *sia* (for municipalities).
- Other parameters:** The parameter *sia_threshold* is set to 0.5, as this value corresponds to the highest *sia* values of WWTP operators without sensors, thus avoiding a large 'jump' of sensor adoption at the beginning of the simulation (Figure F.2). *pb*c_threshold, which is set to 0.2, as the lowest *pb*c of agents with sensors lies around that value. The value of μ , determining the degree of influence on *sia* per interaction of two agents, is set to 0.01, such that the form of the curve looks reasonable.
- Schedule:** The communication schedule (frequency only) was provided by the expert and is shown in Table F.1. The estimation relates to the canton of Bern and includes exchange between stakeholders involved in the planning or revision of a GEP. The exchange among agents starts simultaneously, as the start table (Table F.2) is left at its default state (zero matrix).

Table F.1: Communication schedule baseline scenario - frequency table (meeting every X months)

	WWTP operator	Cantonal Authority	Municipality	Engineer
WWTP operator	1	3	12	3
Cantonal Authority	3	1	12	3
Municipality	12	12	12	3
Engineer	3	3	3	1

Table F.2: Communication schedule baseline scenario - start table (first meeting after X months)

	WWTP operator	Cantonal Authority	Municipality	Engineer
WWTP operator	0	0	0	0
Cantonal Authority	0	0	0	0
Municipality	0	0	0	0
Engineer	0	0	0	0

²Genereller Entwässerungsplan

Figure F.2: The share of WWTP operators with sensors over the simulation period of 10 years in the baseline scenario, while the parameter *sia_threshold* is varied. (20 runs for each value). It can be seen that with a lower value of *sia_threshold*, the share of WWTP operators with sensors is higher. For a value of *sia_threshold*, a jump is observed in the first time step, when the agents with *sia* higher than the threshold adopt sensors.

Figure F.3: The share of municipalities with sensors over the simulation period of 10 years in the baseline scenario, while the parameter *sia_threshold* is varied. (20 runs for each value). It can be seen that with a lower value of *sia_threshold*, the share of municipalities with sensors is higher.

Figure F.4: The share of WWTP operators with sensors over the simulation period of 10 years in the baseline scenario, while the parameter *pbcthreshold* is varied. (20 runs for each value). It can be seen that with a lower value of *sia_threshold*, the share of WWTP operators with sensors is higher.

F.2 Scenario 1 - Without GEP

Description:	This scenario is an adaptation of the baseline scenario (Section F.1). All parameters are kept the same as in the baseline scenario, except for the communication schedule which is adapted to simulate a less frequent exchange among the actors involved in the GEP.
Purpose:	Evaluating the influence of a regular exchange among the actors involved in the planning and revision of a GEP on sensor adoption among municipalities and WWTP operators by simulating a scenario without GEP.
Social network:	The same as in baseline scenario.
Agent initialization:	The same as in baseline scenario.
Other parameters:	The same as in baseline scenario.
Schedule:	The communication schedule is shown in Table F.3. Compared to the baseline scenario, the communication among actors involved in the GEP is reduced. Namely, the exchange between the municipalities and the cantonal authorities, between the cantonal authorities and the engineers, and between the engineers and the municipalities happens less frequently

Table F.3: Communication schedule model configuration 6 - frequency table (meeting every X months)

	WWTP operator	Cantonal Authority	Municipality	Engineer
WWTP operator	1	3	12	3
Cantonal Authority	3	1	0	6
Municipality	12	0	12	6
Engineer	3	6	6	1

F.3 Scenario 2 - Regulation

Description:	This scenario is an adaptation of the baseline scenario (Section F.1), simulating the introduction of a regulation prescribing the adoption of sensors.
Purpose:	Evaluating the effect of the policy 'regulation'.
Social network:	The same as in the baseline scenario.
Agent initialization:	The introduction of a regulation is assumed to change the normative beliefs and the subjective norm of WWTP operators and municipalities in favor of sensor adoption if they have not yet a sensor adopted. Thus, these agent's <i>sia</i> is gradually increased (by 0.01 each time step), starting with the introduction of the regulation (2020) and ending 24 time steps later (2022). The increased amount is arbitrary.
Other parameters:	The same as in the baseline scenario.
Schedule:	The communication frequency is the same as in the baseline scenario (Table F.1) without shift in time (Table F.2).

Figure F.5: Opinion dynamics including 2966 agents for Scenario 2 'regulation'. The increase of sia through the regulation affects all agents that have not adopted sensors (yet). The municipalities are most affected by the regulation that increases their sia over the $sia_threshold$, while the increase of sia is not strong enough for a large part of the WWTP operators to adopt sensors.

F.4 Scenario 3 - Better Technology

- Description:** This scenario is an adaptation of the baseline scenario (Section F.1), simulating the introduction of better technology into the market.
- Purpose:** Evaluating the effect of the policy 'Better technology'.
- Social network:** The same as in the baseline scenario.
- Agent initialization:** The same as in the baseline scenario.
- Other parameters:** The parameter $pb_threshold$ is initialized at 0.2 like in the other model configurations. However, it is decreased by a small amount every time step such that at the end of the simulation period it reaches 0.
- Schedule:** The communication frequency is the same as in the baseline scenario (Table F.1) without shift in time (Table F.2).

F.5 Numerical experiment 1 - Shifted communication schedule

- Description:** This scenario is an adaptation of the baseline scenario (Section F.1). All parameters are kept the same as in the baseline scenario, except for the interactions between agents, which happen at the same frequency but are shifted in time.
- Purpose:** Evaluating the influence of agent interactions happening in a different order on the model outcome. As the agents interact with each other at the same frequency as in the baseline scenario (except at the beginning), no large difference in outcome is expected. However, if the results are

largely different, this leads to the conclusion that interaction order plays an important role.

Social network: The same as in the baseline scenario.

Agent initialization: The same as in the baseline scenario.

Other parameters: The same as in the baseline scenario.

Schedule: The communication frequency is the same as in the baseline scenario (Table F.1). However, the interactions are shifted in time by the number of (monthly) time steps that are listed in Table F.4.

Table F.4: Communication schedule model configuration 2 - start table (first meeting after X months)

	WWTP operator	Cantonal Authority	Municipality	Engineer
WWTP operator	0	2	3	1
Cantonal Authority	2	0	3	2
Municipality	3	3	3	2
Engineer	1	2	2	0

F.6 Numerical experiment 2 - Different communication schedule

Description: The communication schedule from baseline scenario is altered, according to the estimation of a different expert³.

Purpose: Analyzing the influence of uncertainties concerning the communication schedule input on the model output, assuming that both experts provide a valid estimation.

Social network: The same as in baseline scenario.

Agent initialization: The same as in baseline scenario.

Other parameters: The same as in baseline scenario.

Schedule: The communication schedule (frequency only) was provided by a different expert than in the baseline scenario and is shown in Table F.5. The exchange among agents starts simultaneously, as the start table (Table F.2) is left at its default state (zero matrix).

³Joerg Rieckermann on 15.02.2021

Table F.5: Communication schedule model configuration 3 - frequency table (meeting every X months)

	WWTP operator	Cantonal Authority	Municipality	Engineer
WWTP operator	1	12	6	12
Cantonal Authority	12	3	1	1
Municipality	6	1	12	3
Engineer	12	1	3	3

F.7 Numerical experiment 3 - Cantonal authorities' network

Description: This scenario is an adaptation of the baseline scenario (Section F.1). All parameters are kept the same as in the baseline scenario while the network among cantonal authorities is configured differently.

Purpose: Evaluating the effect of a different network configuration, simulating the effect of a more opportunities for opinion exchange among cantonal authorities, communicating on national level.

Social network: The cantonal authorities are linked through a fully connected network instead of only being linked to their immediate geographical neighbors. The rest of the network is the same as in the baseline scenario. In total, there are 325 edges among the cantonal authorities. In comparison to the social network used in the baseline scenario, there are 325 instead of 57 links between the cantonal authorities.

Agent initialization: The same as in the baseline scenario.

Other parameters: The same as in the baseline scenario.

Schedule: The communication frequency is the same as in the baseline scenario (Table F.1) without shift in time (Table F.2).

F.8 Numerical experiment 4 - Random opinion uncertainty

Description: This scenario is an adaptation of the baseline scenario (Section F.1). The only variation concerns the assignment of the uncertainty u .

Purpose: Analyzing uncertainties regarding the relative agreement algorithm for opinion exchange. Several methods for the assignment of u could be found in the papers. [Caprioli et al., 2020] propose a random assignment of u while [Rai and Robinson, 2015] initialize it proportional to the inverse absolute value of sia . This scenario will be used to compare both methods.

Social network: The same as in the baseline scenario.

Agent initialization: The uncertainty u is not assigned inversely proportional to the extremity of sia as in the baseline scenario, but according to a uniform distribution taking the values between 0.01 and 1. The smallest uncertainty is chosen > 0 to avoid division by 0 in the RA Algorithm

Other parameters: The same as in the baseline scenario.

Schedule: The communication frequency is the same as in the baseline scenario (Table F.1) without shift in time (Table F.2).

G Sensitivity Analysis

G.1 Parameter range

Looking at Figure 2.6 and Figure 2.7, it is noted that there is an overlap of *sia* between agents that have sensors adopted and agents that have not. Thus, no clear threshold can be identified above which an agent adopts sensors. With respect to the agents that have no sensors adopted but display a high *sia* (around 0.5), it is assumed that *sia_threshold* varies between 0.4 and 0.6. *pbc_threshold* was varied between 0 and 0.3, as the lowest *pbc* displayed by agents with sensors adopted lies at 0.2. Thus, it must be possible to adopt sensors with this value of *pbc*. For μ no clear estimate can be given, as no historical data is available about sensor adoption in CSO tanks. It is set between 0.01 and 0.1.

G.2 Sampling Agent Parameters

For the sensitivity analysis, the following agent parameters are transformed into model parameters by sampling them from a distribution and then considering the mean of the distribution as a model parameter.

Agent parameters

<i>sia</i>	Opinion / attitude
<i>pbc</i>	Perceived behavioural control
<i>u</i>	Uncertainty of opinion
<i>sensor_installed</i>	Whether the agent has a sensor installed or not

This leads to the parameters listed in Table G.1 that are varied in the SA. The lower and upper bounds of the distributions refer to the distributions in Figure G.1. The share of WWTP operators / municipalities with sensors determines how many agents are assigned *sensor_installed* = True. If an agent has a sensor installed, her *sia* and *pbc* are drawn from the distributions on the right hand side of Figure G.1, if not from the left hand side, respectively. Engineers' and cantonal authorities' parameters are drawn from the right hand side. As *sia* and *pbc* are assumed to correlate (Figure 2.6), both are drawn from the same distribution. The form of the distribution of *sia* and *pbc* in Figure 2.7 resemble to a gamma distribution rather than a normal distribution. Furthermore, the distributions estimated by an expert in the questionnaire can be compared to a gamma distribution.

Figure G.1: The distributions from which the agent parameters are sampled.

Table G.1: Parameter bounds for the sensitivity analysis

Parameter	Lower bound	Upper bound
sia_threshold	0.4	0.6
psc_threshold	0.0	0.3
mu	0.01	0.1
Share of WWTP operators with sensors	50%	75%
Share of municipalities with sensors	20%	45%
Dist. WWTP operators with sensors	[b.r.] 11	[t.r.] 3
Dist. WWTP operators without sensors	[t.l.] 3	[b.l.] 11
Dist. Municipalities with sensors	[b.r.] 11	[t.r.] 3
Dist. Municipalities without sensors	[t.l.] 3	[b.l.] 11
Dist. Cantonal authorities	[b.r.] 11	[t.r.] 3
Dist. Engineers	[b.r.] 11	[t.r.] 3

[t.l.], [t.r.], [b.l.], [b.r.] refer to Figure G.1, to the distributions top left, top right, bottom left and bottom right, respectively.

G.3 Additional Results

G.3.1 Full scatter plot by parameters

G.3.2 Other performance metrics

In this section, further performance metrics are analysed. All the following figures either relate to the share of WWTP operators with sensors adopted or the share of municipalities with sensors adopted, respectively. However, there is the possibility of analyzing the behavior of these metrics at different time steps of the simulation period.

Figure G.2: Total share of municipalities with sensors after 120 time steps by entry parameter.

Figure G.3: Increase of share of WWTP operators (from t_0 to t_{120}) with sensors after 120 time steps by entry parameter.

Figure G.4: Morris co-variance plot: increase of share of WWTP operators (from t_0 to t_{120}) with sensors.

Figure G.5: Morris co-variance plot: total share of Municipalities with sensors after 120 time steps.

Figure G.6: Morris co-variance plot: The analyzed metric is the increase ('jump') of WWTP operators (above) and municipalities (below) with sensors after the first time step (from t_0 to t_1) which occurs due to all agents that are initialized with *sia* above the threshold adopting sensors.

Figure G.7: Morris co-variance plot: The analyzed metric is the increase of WWTP operators (above) and municipalities (below) with sensors between the first time step and the last one (from t_0 to t_{120})

H Development History

In this chapter, the larger steps in the development history of the prototype are described.

H.1 Starting point

A first study regarding ABM for sensor adoption was performed at Eawag [Ladner, 2020].

H.2 Model 1

The first prototype concept is illustrated in Figure H.1. The central variable of the model is the perceived utility of sensors (PUS), which leads to the adoption of a sensor if it crosses a certain threshold. Similar to the RA algorithm used for opinion dynamics, the agents change their PUS upon the influence of other agents. The central agent is the CSO operator, which has a strong connection to the WWTP operator if the WWTP and CSO tanks are operated by the same organization. The model described in Figure H.1 is a subsystem of a larger system described in Figure H.2.

Figure H.1: The first model draft including one catchment area. In the boxes of the agents, the agent behavior is described in a pseudo-algorithm.

Figure H.3 illustrates the first model that was implemented in the **Mesa** framework. For demonstration purposes, it is simpler than the model from Figure H.1. It is based on the concept of

Figure H.2: The hierarchy of subsystems regarding the first model draft.

'awareness', i.e. the awareness of the usefulness of sensors. Agents that are aware, e.g. the cantonal authority, spread awareness through giving 'stimuli' to their neighboring agents. If an agent has received a certain amount of stimuli (awareness threshold), it becomes aware itself and starts spreading awareness. The spreading of awareness takes place on a social network as illustrated in Figure H.4, similar to the spreading of a virus. In Figure 3, the simulation results are shown for a time step of half a year and 10 model runs each for 3 different awareness thresholds. The agents chose a random neighbor to influence each time step, which leads to the different trajectories of the share of aware agents for each run.

Figure H.3: Schema of the first implemented model. The pseudo-algorithm of agent-behavior is included in the descriptive boxes of each agent type.

Agent Behavior To this point, of modeling, three different options were considered for agent behavior leading to sensor adoption:

1. The agent's perceived usefulness of sensors crosses a certain threshold
2. The agent becomes aware of the use of sensors through stimuli from others. If the agent

Figure H.4: Test network for the first implemented model.

Figure H.5: Results of the 'awareness'-model running on the test network. The different colors illustrate the share of aware agents for different awareness thresholds.

received more than X stimuli, it adopts a sensor.

3. The agent optimizes a cost function.

In the next section, the agent behavior is described through decision trees in a flowchart.

H.3 Model 2

In Figure H.6, the simplest version of Model 2 is described. The agents' behavior depends largely on the value of the parameter P , which stands for personality. Each time step, an agent will act with a probability P . The WWTP operator is the only agent type that adopts sensors. If the WWTP operator is aware of the use of sensors, she will adopt a sensor. The cantonal authority and the engineer raise awareness among other agents for the use of sensors ('awareness request'). The 'awareness' spreads through the social network of the agents like a virus, where each agent has a probability P of infecting itself. In Figures H.7, H.8, H.9, H.10, the results for this model version are shown. P is first varied for all agents simultaneously (Figure H.7), then varied for each agent separately. It can be seen by comparisons of Figures H.8, H.9, H.10, that the variation of P of the authority has the largest effect on the share of aware agents ('Awareness'). The reason for this is that the cantonal authority is the only aware agent at the beginning of the simulation, but also occupies a central place in the network. If it only 'infects' others with awareness each time step with e.g. a very low probability of P , this has a larger impact on the overall share of aware agents, than e.g. a very low P of a WWTP operator.

Extended version

In Figure H.11, an extended version of Model 2 is described, that was not implemented. The extended version includes a financial, know-how, and decision power layer. The layers have the following meanings:

Awareness	If an agent is aware of the use of sensors or not.
Financial	If an agent has the financial resources to adopt a sensor - in TPB this would be expressed through <i>pb</i> .
Know-how	If an agent has the know-how to adopt a sensor. In TPB, this has an impact on <i>pb</i> and <i>sia</i> .
Decision power	If an agent has the 'key' to a CSO tank and can install a sensor in it.

Figure H.6: The 'awareness' model flowchart, including factor P.

Figure H.7: Varying P for all agents in the 'awareness' model simultaneously for the whole of Switzerland.

Figure H.8: Varying P for the WWTP operator agents while the other agents' P is kept at 0.2. Eastern Switzerland included.

Figure H.9: Varying P for the municipality agents while the other agents' P is kept at 0.2. Eastern Switzerland included.

Figure H.10: Varying P for the cantonal authority agents while the other agents' P is kept at 0.2. Eastern Switzerland included.

Figure H.11: The extended 'awareness' model flowchart, including financial, know-how, and decision power layer.

I Expert Questionnaires

An empty version of the questionnaire on the following pages. For more information, please contact the author.

Fragebogen - Expertenvalidierung eines agentenbasierten Modells

In einer Masterarbeit im Rahmen des POLAAR-Projekts werden die Prozesse untersucht, die zum Einbau von Sensoren in Mischwasserüberlaufbecken (CSO) führen. Genauer gesagt, die Installation von Wasserstandsmessern zur Quantifizierung der Tankfüllung und des Überlaufs sowie zur Abschätzung der Überlaufmengen. Die damit gesammelten Daten haben das Potenzial, den täglichen Betrieb von CSOs, die Planung zukünftiger CSOs und die Leistungsbewertung hinsichtlich der Einhaltung von Umweltauflagen zu verbessern. Allerdings sind diese Sensoren derzeit in der Schweiz noch nicht weit verbreitet. Da die Technologie für die Überwachung von CSOs existiert und an einigen Orten bereits implementiert wurde, interessieren wir uns für die organisatorischen und politischen Aspekte, die zur Einführung von Sensoren in CSOs führen. Insbesondere möchten wir die Auswirkungen möglicher Maßnahmen, wie Gesetze, technischen Richtlinien oder lokalen Peer-Events zur Wissensbildung über die evidenzbasierte Leistungsbewertung von Abwasserkanälen/CSOs vorhersagen. Angefangen bei der Installation von Wasserstandsmessern in CSO-Tanks, die es ermöglichen, die Funktion und Leistung der Infrastruktur zu beurteilen.

Um unser Verständnis zu verbessern, haben wir uns entschieden, ein Modell zu erstellen, das die wichtigsten Stakeholder in der Schweizer Siedlungswasserwirtschaft einbezieht, die für die Installation von Sensoren in CSO-Tanks relevant sind. Wir modellieren die Stakeholder innerhalb eines agentenbasierten Modells (ABM), das in den Sozialwissenschaften und anderen Gebieten verwendet wird. In unserem Fall ist ein Agent eine computerprogrammierte Vereinfachung eines realen Akteurs. Diese Agenten interagieren mit ihrer Umgebung und den anderen Agenten. Um ein plausibles Modell zu erstellen, ist das Wissen von Domänenexperten entscheidend.

Die Agenten und ihre Interaktionen

Die Stakeholder, auf die wir uns in diesem Modell konzentrieren, sind die kantonalen Behörden und die Kläranlagenbetreiber*innen, die GEP-Spezialist*innen und die Gemeinden (s. Abbildung 2). Die kantonale Fachstelle ist für die Siedlungsentwässerung in ihrem Kanton zuständig. Ihre Hauptaufgabe ist es, den Vollzug des Schweizerischen Gewässerschutzgesetzes sicherzustellen. Die Kläranlagenbetreiber sorgen für den effizienten und ordnungsgemäßen Betrieb der Kläranlagen. Da die Organisationsstrukturen in der schweizerischen Siedlungswasserwirtschaft sehr vielfältig sind, werden Vereinfachungen vorgenommen und verschiedene Stakeholder unter einem der vier oben genannten Akteure zusammengefasst (s. Abbildung 1). Unter dem Begriff Kläranlagenbetreiber fassen wir alle Akteure zusammen, die mit einer bestimmten Kläranlage verbunden sind, also Verbände, Betreiberin, Klärwärter etc. Die GEP-Spezialist*in ist am GEP-Check beteiligt, um eine Gesamtplanung der Kläranlagen und der Abwasserinfrastruktur für jede Gemeinde zu ermitteln. Schließlich umfasst der Begriff Gemeinde alle an die Gemeinde angeschlossenen Akteure, vom Tiefbauamt bis zum Gemeinderat.

Abbildung 1: Vereinfachung eines realen Netzwerks

Ihre Aufgabe

Die folgende Tabelle beschreibt einige Annahmen, die dazu dienen, die reale Welt zu vereinfachen und so zu vereinfachen, dass sie in einem Computer programmiert werden kann. Die Annahmen beziehen sich sowohl auf das Verhalten der Akteure als auch auf die Interaktionen zwischen den Akteuren. Bitte teilen Sie uns mit, welchen der folgenden Annahmen Sie zustimmen, nur teilweise zustimmen oder gar nicht zustimmen. Im folgenden werden Ihnen ebenfalls offene Fragen gestellt. Bitte beantworten Sie diese einfach nach bestem Wissen. Vielen Dank!

Annahme	Einverstanden?		
	ja	teilweise	nein
Die Kantonale Fachstelle ist relevant für die Installierung von Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB.			
Die GEP-Spezialist*in ist relevant für die Installierung von Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB.			
Die Betreiberin der ARA ist relevant für die Installierung von Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB.			
Die Gemeinde ist relevant für die Installierung von Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB.			
Über die Installation eines Wasserstandssensors im RÜB entscheidet in der Regel entweder die Gemeinde oder die Betreiberin der ARA.			
Über die Installation eines Wasserstandssensors im RÜB entscheidet in der Regel nicht die Kantonale Fachstelle oder die GEP-Spezialist*in.			

Gibt es ausser den oben genannten 4 Stakeholdern noch weitere Stakeholder, die im Modell berücksichtigt werden sollten?

Falls Ja, bitte listen sie diese hier auf:

Bitte stufen Sie ein, wie relevant folgende Firmen in der GEP-Planung sind. Falls Sie noch weitere relevante Firmen kennen, notieren Sie diese bitte in den leeren Plätzen am Ende der Tabelle.

0=nicht relevant, 1=wenig relevant, 2= relevant, 3=sehr relevant

Firma	Einstufung
Hunziker Betatech	
Holinger AG	
BG21	
TBF	
Pöyry / AFRY	
CSD	

Offizielle Events

Gerne würden wir etwas besser abschätzen können, welche Events Möglichkeiten zum Austausch über Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB bieten. Wie viel Prozent der Agenten nehmen ungefähr an den Folgenden Meetings Teil? Bitte tragen Sie den entsprechenden Prozentsätze in die untenstehende Tabelle ein.

Falls Ihnen noch ein weiterer relevanter Event einfällt, tragen Sie diesen bitte ebenfalls rechts in die Tabelle ein.

Beim *Tiefbauamtstag* handelt es sich um eine fiktive Veranstaltung, an der die Tiefbauämter (Agent: Gemeinde) teilnehmen würden. Wir haben vor, diese Veranstaltung als Policy im Modell zu implementieren.

	GEP-Check	Klärmeistertag	<i>Tiefbauamtstag</i>	
Betreiber ARA				
Kant. Fachstelle				
Municipality				
GEP-Ingenieur				

Austausch ausserhalb von offiziellen Events

Gerne würden wir ebenfalls besser einschätzen können, welche Stakeholder untereinander in regem Austausch stehen und welche nicht. Bitte teilen Sie uns Ihre Einschätzung in der untenstehenden Tabelle mit der folgenden Skala mit. Die geschwärzten Felder sind redundant, müssen nicht ausgefüllt werden.

0=nie, 1=1x pro Jahr, 2=Alle 3 Monate, 3=einmal im Monat oder mehr

	Betreiberin ARA	Kant. Fachstelle GEP	Gemeinde	GEP-Spezialist*in
Betreiberin ARA				
Kant. Fachstelle GEP				
Gemeinde				
GEP-Spezialist*in				

Frage	An offiziellen Events	Ausserhalb offizieller Events
Werden Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB eher an offiziellen Events oder ausserhalb davon diskutiert?		

Einstellung zu Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB

Aus Umfragen bei Abwasserverbänden und Kantonalen Fachstellen, kombiniert mit Geodaten über ARAs, haben wir einen Index errechnet, der die Einstellung zu Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB abbilden soll. In den Index fließen soziale Faktoren ein (z.B. die Motivation der Kantonalen Fachstelle), die Vision des zukünftigen Abwassersystems (z.B. Real-time control) und Erfahrung im Umgang mit Messtechnik ein.

Der Index liegt zwischen 0 und 1:

0 bedeutet: Keine erfahrung mit Messtechnik ausserhalb der Kläranlage, kein Betrieb von Regenbecken, Ablehnung der Vision von integralem Einzugsgebietsmanagement und Real-Time-control, keine Motivation seitens der Kantonalen Fachstelle und wenig Wasserstandssensoren in den RÜB im Kanton.

1 bedeutet: Sensoren installiert in allen betriebenen RÜB, Erfassung diversen Messwerten wie Entlastungsdauer, -menge und -häufigkeit, Zustimmung der Vision von integralem Einzugsgebietsmanagement und RTC, Motivation von und gute Zusammenarbeit mit der Kant. Fachstelle, Teilnahme an Events zur Wissensvermittlung.

Annahme	Einverstanden?		
	ja	teilweise	nein
Die Verteilung der Einstellung unter ARA-Betreiberinnen zu Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB ist plausibel.			
Die Einstellung von Verbänden zu Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB entspricht ungefähr der Einstellung von anders organisierten ARA-Betreiberinnen.			

Da uns keine Daten zur Einstellung von Gemeinden oder GEP-Spezialist*innen vorliegen, würden wir gerne Ihre Einschätzung dazu ins Modell einfließen lassen. Bitte schätzen Sie die Form der Verteilung und zeichnen Sie sie in die leeren Graphen auf der vorherigen Seite, z. B. mit der Kurvenfunktion von Word (Einfügen > Formen > Kurve, Bsp.: Graph Betreiberin ARA).

Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB im Verlauf der Zeit.

Es liegen uns ebenfalls keine historischen Daten über die Verbreitung von Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB in der Schweiz vor. Bitte schätzen Sie die vergangene und zukünftige Verbreitung von Sensoren für Gemeinden und ARA-Betreiberinnen und zeichnen sie in diese in die folgenden zwei leeren Graphen.

Ziehen sie dazu bitte die blauen Punkte am unteren Rand auf die gewünschte Höhe im Graphen.

Betreiberinnen ARA mit Wasserstandssensoren in RÜB

Vielen Dank, dass Sie sich die Zeit genommen haben! Bitte senden Sie mir den ausgefüllten Fragebogen an derworts@ethz.ch.